

The Mediating Effect of Employee Motivation On the Relationship between Professional Knowledge and Instructional Strategies

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APPROVAL SHEET

This study entitled “**THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDEGE AND INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES**”, prepared and submitted by **JUVIE O. BANGCASAN**, in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree Master of Arts in Education Major in Technology and Livelihood Education, has been examined and is hereby recommended for approval and acceptance.

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the mediating effect of employee motivation on the relationship between professional knowledge and teachers' instructional strategies. A non-experimental quantitative research design using the descriptive-correlational technique was employed. There were 300 Technology Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers in the Division of Davao de Oro were chosen through simple random sampling. The study used three adapted instruments to gather the data from the respondents. The tools used in analyzing the data were Mean, Pearson r, Regression, and Medgraph using the Sobel z-test. Results show that the TLE teachers posted a very high-level professional knowledge, instructional strategies of teachers, and a high level of employee motivation. Findings also revealed a significant relationship between professional knowledge and teachers' instructional strategies, professional knowledge and employee motivation, and teacher motivation and instructional strategies. Further, the study found that employee motivation significantly mediates the relationship between professional knowledge and teachers' instructional strategies. With this current proposition, TLE teachers who are highly motivated and knowledgeable about their work influence their instructional strategies in teaching.

Keywords:- *TLE Education, professional knowledge, instructional strategies, employee motivation, mediation, teacher, Philippines*

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CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

A. *Rationale*

An instructional strategy is a process in which teachers use a variety of strategies to communicate with students about academic topics, engage them in conversation, and promote their learning (Htun & Lynch, 2019). However, teachers became ineffective in their teaching due to being overburdened with new policies, standards and a lack of instructional leadership, making it difficult to find adequate time and energy to engage in what was needed in school. This leads teachers to encounter issues with instructional strategies when students cannot accomplish tasks or meet goals effectively (Steiner & Kowal, 2017).

Instructional strategies serve to be teachers' backbone for teaching. There are various instructional strategies where effective transmission of ideas and enhanced learning in subject areas are assured (Persaud, 2018). Accordingly, direct or indirect education, experiential learning, independent study, or interactive instruction are all examples of instructional strategies (Salleh, Sari, Hassan, Yusof, & Salleh, 2022). Instructional strategies are the most potent and satisfying tool in delivering instructions, such as active learning, group-based, assessment-based, and organizational activities. These teaching methods are easily accessible to teachers employing technology. However, teachers still require professional expertise to make even tricky subject matter approachable and to enable ideas to develop fully and logically (Persaud, 2018).

Moreover, Fortsch, Fortsch, Von Kotzebue, and Neuhaus (2018) acknowledged that teachers' knowledge and viewpoints of the subject matter significantly influence instructional strategies. In addition, teachers' motivation helps to develop their professional knowledge and instructional strategies and is vital in the teaching process. The professional knowledge and the instructional strategies imparted are closely linked and rely on one another. Still, developing teachers' motivation helps to function their knowledge and will connect to how they deliver their instructional strategies to clientele. Exposing the content knowledge and teaching strategy requires an intimate and sophisticated knowledge of motivation and enthusiasm (Nilsson, 2018).

According to a study conducted in the Philippines by Toquero and Talidong (2021) on implementing effective instructional strategies, it is critical to capture the learners' attention to participate in a class. Teachers place a high value on their student's participation. Unfortunately, most teachers are uninterested in attracting students' attention to class collaboration. In addition, some job descriptions for teachers make it impossible for them to function well. They were so preoccupied with the paperwork of their coordinator ship that they sometimes needed to remember their most important job, which was developing instructional strategies. They needed to be more focused on allocating time and resources to beautify their rooms, ignoring the primary role of providing quality education to learners by ensuring that the competencies were met (Caingcoy, 2020).

With this idea in mind, the researcher believes that preparing instructional materials and employing instructional strategies in instructional planning is more enhanced if someone is motivated. It can significantly affect a high learning outcome and allows someone to go the extra mile. However, there is a dearth of studies and empirical evidences regarding the relationship between professional knowledge and instructional strategies. On the other hand, teacher motivation is an essential factor closely related to several factors in education, such as student motivation, teaching practice, and teachers' psychological fulfillment and well-being. Teacher motivation is vital to other areas related to professional knowledge and instructional strategy (Han & Yin, 2018). Along this disposition, the researcher is prompted to explore this gap. The study is significant to the Department of Education and the University responsible for producing these teachers.

B. *Research Objective*

This study aimed to determine the mediating effect of employee motivation on the relationship between professional knowledge and instructional strategies. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following objectives:

- To identify the level of professional knowledge of teachers in terms of:
 - ✓ subject- matter knowledge;
 - ✓ curricular knowledge;
 - ✓ pedagogical knowledge; and
 - ✓ learners' knowledge.
- To determine the level of instructional strategies utilized by teachers in terms of:
 - ✓ Instructional strategies;
 - ✓ Content expectation;
 - ✓ Cognitive challenge; and
 - ✓ Questioning.

- To describe the level of employee motivation of teachers in terms of:
 - ✓ Basic needs;
 - ✓ Safety;
 - ✓ Esteem;
 - ✓ Love; and
 - ✓ Self-actualization.
- To determine the significant relationship between professional knowledge and instructional strategies of teachers.
- To assess the significant relationship between professional knowledge and the employee motivation of teachers.
- To identify the significant relationship between employee motivation and the instructional strategies of teachers.
- To evaluate the mediating effect of employee motivation on the relationship between professional knowledge and instructional strategies of teachers.

C. Hypothesis

The following hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

- There is no significant relationship between professional knowledge and the instructional strategies of teachers.
- There is no significant relationship between professional knowledge and employee motivation among teachers.
- There is no significant relationship between employee motivation and the instructional strategies of teachers.
- There is no mediating effect on employee motivation on the relationship between professional knowledge and instructional strategies of teachers.

D. Review of Related Literature

This section discusses multiple perspectives, discussions, theories, outcomes, and synthesis from research, journals, and articles relevant to the dependent variable, which is the professional knowledge whose dimensions are *subject-matter knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, and learner knowledge* (Warnock, 2015). The dependent variable is the instructional strategies with the following indicators, *instructional strategies, content and expectation, cognitive challenge, and questioning* (Warnock, 2015). The mediating variable is employee motivation, with indicators of *basic needs, safety, esteem, love, and self-actualization* (Nohria, Groysberg, & Lee, 2008).

➤ Professional Knowledge

Teachers are essential in ensuring that students obtain a high-quality education. Various research investigations have proven that the quality of an educational system can only be measured by the quality of its teachers. Teachers must continuously train and renew their knowledge to remain productive and competitive in today's technology-based learning environment (Danielewicz, 2021). In addition, teachers' education cannot fully prepare them with the necessary knowledge and skills for lifelong learning. Simply, learning does not end with graduation; rather, the rest of a teacher's career should be an ongoing effort to learn and develop (Garzón Artacho, 2020).

Teachers are believed to have a wide range of knowledge that informs decisions about what to teach and how to teach it (Elbaz, 2018). According to Caena (2019), teachers must be mentors who develop reliable connections with students, coordinators of individual and group learning, alchemists who combine strategies, techniques, and resources to spark students' creativity, welders who join disparate bits of knowledge and activities into an integral whole, and collaborators who fully understand and deploy both their own and other's potential. In this way, teachers improve their professional knowledge and gain a better understanding of how to fulfill their students' needs effectively (Persaud, 2018).

Moreover, Professional development promotes professional knowledge and competence in a changing environment with diverse and multiple teacher roles. Professional development has a significant positive relationship with professional knowledge and competence (Yuan, Wu, Chen, & Li, 2017). Teachers' professional knowledge shapes strategies and guidelines for the teaching profession's planning, certification, hiring, and evaluation (Salleh, 2022). Furthermore, it will aid in implementing programs and activities that provide teachers with continuing professional development. (Baumert et al., 2019).

Similarly, teachers' knowledge of the subject taught at school and related to the teaching process is critical (Bennett & Carre, 2017). In connection, educators' professional knowledge, teaching skills, attitudes, and self-reflection capacities advance the quality and effectiveness and consistently take an interest in various pedagogies (Lovat & Clement, 2018). However, the process of improving teachers' knowledge and skills is dependent on several factors, such as the availability of effective professional development programs, teachers' availability and readiness to learn and unlearn, teachers' commitment to applying what they have learned and skills they have gained, and teachers' job satisfaction and motivation (Armour & Yelling, 2017).

According to Schleicher (2018), each teacher possesses enough general knowledge, professional knowledge, competence, and professionalism through continuous active participation in learning actions and activities that help achieve professional development at both personal and organizational levels to serve society further. Improved teaching knowledge and competence enhance teaching quality, student learning outcomes, self-development, and self-actualization (Madani, 2019).

Hence, continuous professional development is essential for improving teacher proficiency, professional knowledge, and competence. Teacher competence is attained through continuous learning and development, adapting to changes, assisting with teaching dilemmas, promoting teacher professional knowledge, and expanding teacher functions (Nilsson, 2018). However, there is a consensus on what sorts of learning are substantial for teachers. It is better if the teacher understands what the child thinks. Deliberation of such concerns is addressed by the succeeding information accumulated, which is often an indirect foundation for measuring teacher knowledge (Baumert et al., 2019).

- *Subject Matter Knowledge*

Teachers can only encourage students to learn if they understand the subject matter. Teachers' subject matter knowledge is expected to be required to teach an age-appropriate course, whereas No Child Left Behind unleashes an unprecedented test of students' knowledge (Sadler et al., 2018). Teachers' professional development encompasses professional knowledge, skills, attitudes, and professionalism toward teaching skills, new knowledge, interpersonal communication, organizational knowledge, competence, curriculum design, classroom management, and student counseling (Yuan et al., 2017).

In the study of Han and Yin (2018), the emphasis was on many aspects of teaching, with little emphasis on how teachers must understand the subjects they teach. It provided helpful information and discovered that teachers' knowledge influences student learning. Teachers more knowledgeable about their subject matter give their students a tremendous advantage in the classroom (Sadler et al., 2018).

Thus, Voogt et al. (2017) stated that teacher subject matter knowledge is very significant to the enhancement of teaching and learning. Mastery in teaching refers to how knowledge is organized and understood concerning how it affects students' learning. Teaching is a framework for observing relationships between thinking and doing, theory and practice, students and teacher, and students and subject (Fortsch et al., 2018).

- *Curriculum Knowledge*

Curriculum knowledge generally refers to the knowledge and ability required to understand and the learning norms likely to be met. It includes the lesson, assignments, and tasks assigned. (Lokshyna, 2018). Skilled and practical teachers have a broad understanding of all disciplines and a thorough understanding of the subject's principles. They have exceptional comprehension and abilities that allow them to integrate their knowledge of content, curriculum, learning, teaching, and students. This knowledge enables educators to tailor learning environments to the needs of their students (Lomos et al., 2017).

However, the change in curriculum integration is currently demanding. Secondary school teachers specializing in one subject must now create integrated learning opportunities by connecting multiple subjects (Niemela & Tirri, 2018). A teacher must marshal their knowledge and use pedagogical reasoning to transform the content they have into pedagogical forms such as representations, instructional tasks, and classroom activities that make content understandable to students (Chan & Hume, 2019).

Hence, a teacher's curriculum knowledge should include content aspects most appropriate for their teaching ability, such as knowledge of pedagogical representations, instructional strategies, and prior knowledge and learning difficulties about teaching a specific topic to students from diverse backgrounds and experiences (Deng, 2018). Curriculum knowledge should be customized collaboratively by the teacher and student rather than solely by the teacher. A good curriculum design usually considers teachers' experience and students' needs (Wang et al., 2022).

- *Pedagogical Knowledge*

Pedagogical knowledge is the combination of content and how it is taught by teachers in their capacity as educators. It also includes the teacher's knowledge of the students' learning situations, backgrounds, misconceptions, previous information, and experiences (Gess-Newsome et al., 2017). In addition, an expert teacher has pedagogical content knowledge, clever problem-solving ideas, better adaptation for diverse learners, better decision-making and awareness of classroom happenings, a greater understanding of context, and a broad concern for the welfare of students (Guerriero, 2017).

On the other hand, as Neumann et al. (2018) stated, pedagogical content knowledge has a greater impact on student accomplishment than subject knowledge alone. Nonetheless, only pedagogical content knowledge influences instructional quality. Teachers' knowledge is a multifaceted issue that involves recognizing essential core elements in teaching and learning, the notion of knowledge, and how teachers' knowledge is implemented in the classroom (Gess-Newsome, 2018).

- *Learners' Knowledge*

Teachers know each learner's unique skills in the classroom to effectively target teaching toward students' learning needs (Boyle et al., 2018). In addition, Individual learning needs and learner capabilities can be met through tailored learning activities and support. Teachers and administrators may benefit from promptly intervening in learning procedures by developing new measurements and learning materials to target learners' weaknesses (Gan et al., 2022).

However, despite substantial efforts at enhancing students' skills, it has yet to be studied how a teacher's knowledge of individuals plays a vital role in instruction and learning (Gan et al., 2020). Expressing professional knowledge necessitates a common language in which the implication, application, and importance of the teacher's day-to-day function as a mentor may be expressed. Teachers' understanding of learners has been shaped by what they have learned, heard, or seen and the situations they have encountered (Efu, 2020).

According to Bulathwela et al. (2020), Teachers' awareness of students' prior knowledge is hard to gauge. It is frequently disclosed by teachers' choices for what and how to cover a topic, which necessitates the time and judgment of an experienced observer to evaluate—the chances to grasp how learners with diverse interests and capacities recognize logical thoughts. Indeed, the teacher is a facilitator and attendant to learners in learning (Boyle et al., 2018).

In addition, Abdi et al. (2020) stated that it is difficult for teachers to disregard the significant role of their students. Knowing students entails more than just gathering social or reliable data, such as names and ages, information about their family circles, a little about their family backgrounds, or a few statistics about their academic performance. Teachers' expectations for student academic progress will be more accurate if they know their students well. (Tanaka, 2018).

Thus, most teachers did not engage in systematic and meticulous knowledge of their students. Instead of gathering and analyzing information about their students to better understand them, teachers choose to piece together a general picture based on scraps from compositions or student journals, a clue from students' artwork, a guess from eavesdropping on a conversation, a remark from a parent or last year's teacher, and so on (Pan & Lui, 2022). In some cases, teachers made personal connections with their students, mainly when the students and the teacher's persona shared a common interest in the subject matter (Bodily et al., 2018).

- *Instructional Strategies*

Instructional strategies are utilized during the teaching and learning process, including how to use instructional materials from any source in the teaching and learning process. Teaching strategies are required because teaching and classroom instruction cannot be accomplished solely through techniques or methods (Orlich et al., 2017). Similarly, it should allow educators to address learners' needs and differences (Morrison et al., 2019).

Educators can use instructional strategies to make teaching and learning more memorable, meaningful, fun, and enjoyable. The students actively seek opportunities, keeping them on their toes and wanting more than usual (c & Williams, 2019). Relevance in the learning process is essential to effective instructional strategies that help build and sustain student engagement. Making instruction relevant to real-world problems is a teacher's most potent instructional strategy to boost student learning. This form of teaching helps students to examine, enquire, and meaningfully develop knowledge about real-world issues that are significant to them (Angeli & Valanides, 2019).

According to Kember and Kwan (2020), the academic goals of all students are prioritized over other classroom dynamics in instructional strategies. Teacher-focused instruction, scaffolding, concept mapping, and prior knowledge are instructional components that help students develop cognitive and problem-solving skills. When students' learning is authentic, they are more motivated and engaged, particularly when the real-life tasks they complete have specific outcomes.. When the focus of instruction is meaningful and emphasizes students' knowledge of the world, they perform better (Angeli & Valanides, 2019).

Additionally, in the study of Ghosh, Hefferman & Lan (2020), effective teaching necessitates the ability to select and implement appropriate instructional strategies. Teachers must be able to choose and carry out appropriate instructional strategies to be effective teachers. Effective teaching requires the ability of the teacher to plan, coordinate, and use personal qualities, objectives, and skills in preparing lessons, presentations, and evaluations. Furthermore, teachers must excite students, engage them as active participants in their learning, and use suitable strategies and facilities to improve instructional efficacy (Vovides et al., 2017).

- *Content and Expectation*

The best way to improve instruction and develop teachers' content knowledge is through content and expectation. It was obtaining sophisticated levels of knowledge with a repertoire of instructional methods, strategies, and approaches constantly cultivated to convey learning (Weimer, 2018). The process and the content are both significant. Both are necessary because the content taught and how it is taught are inextricably linked and highly dependent on one another (Gentrup et al., 2020).

Additionally, Weimer (2018) stated that considering content and expectation are inextricably linked, the development of one does not imply the development of the other. This is equivalent to saying that teachers' content knowledge is sophisticated. However, if the methods used to convey such knowledge to students are adequate, instruction will effectively encourage or motivate students to learn. The best teachers are those with less advanced subject knowledge. Instead, the best teachers use a variety of instructional strategies, including those that employ technology and tailor the educational environment to the unique learning needs of individual students (Lamon, 2017).

Thus, Teachers develop student performance expectations and treat students differently based on these expectations. To establish a student-centered learning culture, teachers must adjust their expectations and instructional practices to ensure all students learn at high levels (Tsiplakides & Keramida, 2019). The teacher teaches students when and how to help one another, as well as how to direct their work effectively. In this way, the teacher not only imparts its implications to teaching but also achieves the secondary goal of improving each student's performance (Htun & Lynch, 2019).

- *Cognitive Challenge*

The cognitive challenge entails making students acquire and exhibit higher-order thinking skills and offering in-depth explanations of academic content and higher-order thinking concepts and skills. Instructional materials positively influenced cognitive skill development (van Veen, 2020). This is evident because students recognize, associate, organize, distinguish, evaluate pictures, decode, and use various thinking pedagogical skills during implementation (Salleh et al., 2022).

Accordingly, according to Fortsch et al. (2018), the resources accessible to a teacher while teaching impact how students learn. Students' motivation, stimulation, retention, interest, and effective learning can all be affected by how the learning experience is delivered. Possessing well-structured knowledge facilitates the transfer of old knowledge to new domains while identifying several factors that instructors perceive as barriers to teaching strategies (Nilsson, 2018). These are the availability of time to learn new strategies, concerns about whether students are taught the necessary content, students' reactions to novel teaching techniques, and whether different strategies will work. (Wagner, 2019).

- *Questioning*

The ability to question is an essential indicator of a teacher's effectiveness. Teachers concentrate on providing open-ended questions of consistent quality, giving students time to consider and react when questioned. Learning standards in the twenty-first century are rigorous, requiring students to be active learners and questioners in the classroom (Zhan et al., 2022). Teachers use questioning to help students collaborate, rely more on their own judgment to establish correctness, and learn to reason, conjecture, invent, solve problems, and connect ideas with their applications (Smart & Marshall, 2018).

In the Study of Halim et al. (2018), the art of questioning underpins all teaching and learning. Questioning, at the heart of teaching tasks, promotes recall, enhances the learning process and understanding, develops imaginations and figuring out solutions, stimulates curiosity, and fosters creativity. When used correctly, questioning can be a powerful instructional tool. The types of questions asked, the length of the wait, and the types of responses all play an integral part in the efficient use of questioning (Sasson et al., 2018). The professional use of questioning differs significantly between effective and ineffective teachers (Pham & Hamid, 2018).

- *Employee Motivation*

Employee motivation is hard to achieve, and this concept covers all aspects of individuals' personality as well as the situation in which they perceive such a situation (Forson et al.202). Motivation is a source of influence which affects the way people behave. Administrators must cultivate highly qualified teachers who are actively involved in teaching and learning, open to new concepts and techniques, and devoted to student change throughout their careers (Nyakundi, 2017).

David and Eguzoikpe (2019) stated that Motivation moves a person from dullness to interest. It acts as a operating wheel, directing one's activities. Individual motivation is defined as an active participation and dedication to achieve the desired goals.. Motivation can be defined in several ways, including a general desire or inclination to do something. Dissatisfaction with school officials, low turnover rate, constant shortcoming, inadequate compensation, poor career order, limited promotion opportunities, poor educational resources, insufficient school disciplinary policy, the views and conduct of the principal and other teachers, students' poor work behaviors, and lack of interest in participating in school are all factors that affect motivation (Darmiati et al., 2020).

However, in the study of Nyakundi (2017) it was found that although teacher motivation is essential to the teaching and learning process, many teachers are not very motivated. To achieve the educational objectives in every learning environment, it was necessary to look into the factors affecting teacher motivation in light of this observation. A high level of job discontent, pressure, and exhaustion can have a negative impact on motivation and job performance (Locke & Schattke, 2019).

In addition, Hanaysha (2019) stated that employees' commitment is based on rewards and recognition. Employee motivation relies significantly on rewarding employees. Most organizations have made significant progress by thoroughly implementing their business strategy through well-balanced employee reward and recognition programs. Motivation and efficiency among workers can be increased by offering meaningful recognition; subsequently, an organization's total success is determined by how it keeps its employees motivated and analyzes employee performance for job remuneration. Appreciation and acknowledgment, for example, are essential in encouraging staff and enhancing performance. Corporate training can provide employees with opportunities and a sense of obligation to the company, allowing them to work together to repay the reward they received (Nyakundi, 2017).

Furthermore, externally initiated factors such as income have less influence on teacher motivation. Thus, money has a role at every stage. However, it is not required that money alone can enhance the motivation of every employee, and there are intangibles that are main motivators for the worker's inspiration to perform efficiently. (van der Kolk, 2018). To optimize employee performance, the organization must establish procedures, policies, and reward systems that elevate employee satisfaction and motivation (Locke & Schattke, 2019).

Therefore, Olusadum (2018) asserted that it is vital to comprehend what inspires employees. Individuals at various organizational levels with varying earning power may have distinct motivational values. Hence, what motivates employees at one organizational level may not motivate those at another. When assessing attitudes for motivational purposes, these values can be distinguished by income level and other demographic factors (David & Eguzoikpe, 2019).

- *Basic Needs*

Love and a sense of belonging are fundamental psychological needs. Individuals who have taken physical care of themselves are ready to share themselves with others, such as friends and family members. Employees achieve a high level when they are thrilled with their achievements (Klaeijnsen, 2017). The need to feel competent and recognized through designation and accomplishment is included in this esteemed level. Then, there is the cognitive level, where people conceptually excite and discover themselves. The aesthetic level comes next, encompassing a need for harmony, order, and beauty (Cumplings & Worley, 2019).

- *Safety*

Workplace safety includes all elements that have an effect on employees' health, safety, and well-being (Tamers et al. (2020). These elements can include violence in the workplace, drug, and alcohol abuse, environmental dangers, and unsafe working conditions or procedures (Saleem, Shenbei

Furthermore, according to Kobayashi et al. (2020), successful workplace safety initiatives can significantly affect a company's financial performance. Aside from the hidden gains in retention and productivity such programs provide, organizations with excellent workplace safety rules and records enjoy valuable financial advantages (Christian et al., 2019).

- *Esteem*

Esteem is a reflection of an individual's entire subjective emotional evaluation of their value. It is a verdict about oneself as well as a mindset toward oneself. Self-esteem includes beliefs and feelings including victory, despair, pride, and humiliation (Mase, 2021). Because it has been conceived as a potent predictor of specific outcomes, such as academic success, happiness, marriage and relationship satisfaction, and criminal behavior, self-esteem is appealing as a social psychological construct (Moksnes & Espnes, 2018).

- *Love*

Organizations are preoccupied with measurable performance and efficiency in the real world. However, if managers want to motivate and retain their employees, they must appeal to their employees' passion and desire, which cannot be quantified (Luguetti, 2019). It has been discovered that many organizations need to recognize that an organization is entirely made up of people. Moreover, love motivates people (Luna-Arocas & Tang, 2017).

- *And Self-Actualization*

Self-actualization is putting one's interests, creativity, desire for growth, and ability to be responsible and independent into action. The self-actualized individual exhibits traits such as accountability, independence, democracy, benevolence in relationships, and a desire for improvement (Smith, 2018). There is no doubt that self-actualization entails the inner effort of self-knowledge and comprehension of one's powers and abilities, interests and goals, self-awareness of one's own activities, and the search for essential values. Above all, realizing one's identity and interests through involvement in work benefits the individual, as is loyalty to one's work (Perfilyeva, 2019).

➤ *Correlation between Measures*

Professional knowledge of teachers had a significant relationship with the instructional strategies they used (Watted & Barak, 2018). This means that the better the teaching strategies, the higher the teachers' educational attainment. It also implies that the more years of teaching experience you have, the better your teaching strategy will be (Erina & Perederiy, 2021).

According to Cheung (2017), various teaching strategies are essential for ensuring a harmonious teaching and learning process. The extent to which different teaching strategies are used is related to professional knowledge in teaching. Professional knowledge gained through educational attainment, years of teaching experience, and the extent to which different teaching strategies are used.

In addition, Mahler (2019) also stated that utilizing diverse teaching strategies is a significant factor in a harmonious teaching and learning process. Professional knowledge in teaching has something to do with the extent of the use of different teaching strategies. Professional knowledge gained through educational attainment and several years in teaching and the extent of utilizing different teaching strategies (Cheung, 2017).

Malher et al. (2018) stated that teachers' professional knowledge interacts with their competence in implementing appropriate instructional strategies when teaching their students. The preceding related literature and studies supported the notion that teachers play an essential role in teaching and learning, and acquire professional knowledge. Teachers' practical understanding of the content, curriculum, pedagogy, and learners they work with (Kunter et al., 2018).

Anent to this, the study of Thuy Hang & Hong Van (2020), gaining professional knowledge aid in developing their instructional strategies in the classroom. An effective instructional strategy is only possible if teachers consider the complexities of classroom teaching and learn to acquire instructional strategies that allow them to constantly assess and improve teaching-learning effectiveness (Webster-Wright, 2019).

Professional knowledge and teacher motivation are strongly linked. Improving teachers' motivation is a top priority for national and international policymakers, but teachers' competence and knowledge are critical. Organizations invest heavily in their employees' induction and training and their development, maintenance, and retention (Backfisch et al., 2020). Motivation plays an essential role in the continuous growth of professional knowledge and abilities, center expertise, resources for learning, and strategies in determining educational achievement and accomplishment (Gitonga, 2017).

Moreover, teachers want fair pay that recognizes their professional knowledge, increasing their motivation to perform well in their teaching assignments and their willingness to participate in professional growth activities (Cheon et al., 2018). When basic needs are met, higher-order needs can be realized, which are the foundation of meaningful job satisfaction. When basic necessities are addressed, the urge for professional development and advancement is maintained and promoted. This is due to dissatisfied teachers being forced to leave the profession (Richardson & Watt, 2018).

Over the last decade, employee motivation has been critical in instructional strategies and teachers' psychological fulfillment and well-being (Toropova et al., 2021). Teacher motivation is critical for improving teaching strategies and effectiveness. Teacher motivation elements have been studied in terms of teaching efficacy in terms of teaching techniques, teacher approaches to teaching, teaching practice, and instruction behaviors (Alibakhshi et al., 2020).

Furthermore, Blotnick et al. (2018) indicated several studies investigated the connection between teachers' motivation and teaching strategies. The study found that autonomously motivated teachers used productive (student-centered) teaching strategies, whereas non-autonomously motivated teachers used reproductive (teacher-centered) teaching strategies. Teachers' well-being and satisfaction with their work limit their drive to take part in learning and enhance their teaching practice (Toropova et al., 2021).

Consequently, teachers are driven to remain in their field of teaching, stay involved in educational activities, and improve their instructional strategies. This circumstance has an impact on teachers enthusiasm for their jobs and their willingness to make a difference in their students' learning (Watted & Barak, 2018). Teachers' motivation drives them to seek out better strategies, which undermines their involvement in opportunities for professional development throughout the teaching profession (Gemeda & Tynjala, 2019).

Furthermore, Employee motivation is critical in teachers' delivery of high-quality instructional strategies. A teacher can serve as an organizer, coordinator, manager, and promoter of the advantages of instructional practices with higher standards (Keiler, 2018). The effectiveness of teachers' lessons is crucial for raising students' success levels. Since the principal is the campus's educational leader, they must evaluate the working knowledge and motivation of the faculty about effective instructional strategies and then comprehend the demands of their employees to meet those needs (Blackmore & Sachs, 2017).

The motivating factors of teaching performance considered underlying elements that could shape the relationship between professional knowledge and instructional strategy, which are the variables understudied. Hence, these readings could give the researcher plenty of starting points in conceptualizing and contextualizing questionnaires to fit the local research venues (Keiler, 2018). Therefore, there is a need to gain a deeper understanding of employee motivation, mainly the sources-what influence employee motivation, impacts, and procedures administrators may use to develop encouragement packages for employees (Monsivais & Robbins, 2020).

E. Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Instructional Theory of Reigeluth (1999) and the Expectancy Theory of Heneman and Schwab (1972). Generally, teachers' professional knowledge predicts the instructional strategies employed. It indicates how teachers' professional knowledge is imparted to engage in interaction and appropriate instructional strategies. Stronge (2018) asserted that teachers' professional knowledge, beliefs, and instructional assumptions invariably impact the instructional resources they employ in teaching. This premise is tantamount to saying that professional knowledge is essential in utilizing instructional strategies.

Teachers' professional knowledge had a significant relationship with the instructional strategies. The higher the educational attainment of teachers, the better their teaching strategies. Professional knowledge gained through educational attainment and the number of years in teaching relates to utilizing different instructional strategies (Cheung, 2017). Professional growth through which they can acquire professional knowledge that develops their instructional strategies in teaching. Knowledgeable teachers are guided in familiarizing themselves with various kinds of teaching strategies that they can use inside the classroom (Webster-Wright, 2019).

The study's findings of Sinclair (2008) revealed a significant relationship between motivational factors and teachers' instructional strategies. There is a significant relationship between teachers' experience and job performance. Only motivated and satisfied teachers can help students achieve academic success. Thus, instructional strategies meet the needs of students, and student performance leads to retention (Tehseen & Ul Hadi, 2015).

Furthermore, employee motivation plays a vital role in the delivery of quality instructional strategies by teachers (Blackmore & Sachs, 2017). Employee motivation relates to instructional strategies and teachers' psychological fulfillment and well-being. Teacher motivation enhances teaching strategies and effectiveness (Toropova et al., 2021).

Professional knowledge improves teachers' motivation. It is prioritized as a primary concern of national and international policymakers, but the competence and knowledge of the teachers play a vital role in it (Appova & Arbaugh, 2017). Motivation is essential to the continuing growth of professional knowledge and skills, center competencies, educational resources, and strategies in determining educational success and performance (Gitonga, 2017).

In addition, Backfisch et al. (2020) stated that teachers' professional competence level strongly influences their motivation. Professional competence is the professional knowledge and motivational beliefs that serve as the foundation for mastery of specific professional situations. Both professional knowledge and motivational prerequisites are essential for teachers (Farjon et al., 2019).

The study conducted by Kunter et al. (2013) asserted that teachers are vital actors with strategic roles in school teaching and learning. Moreover, professional competence influences teachers' instructional strategies and motivation. The mastery of their subject field and the ability to manage emotional stability to boost motivation, which can substance academic learning and develop their potential, are indicators of teachers' quality (Wahyuningtyas et al., 2020).

Sumantri and Whardani (2017) also stated that teachers' role in the teaching and learning process is very strategic. The professional competence of a teacher determines the quality of education because it has consequences when they carry out instructional strategies and employees' motivation. Professional competence is a characteristic that distinguishes someone and guides her behavior and thinking in all circumstances; it is long-lasting and can result in the successful performance of one's work, and it frequently manifests itself in one's thoughts, attitudes, and behavior. Teachers' level of professional competence can impact their instructional strategies and motivation (Saeid & Eslaminejad, 2016).

F. Conceptual Framework

Presented in figure 1 is the conceptual framework of the study. The study's independent variable is professional knowledge established by Warnock (2015) with the following indicators; *subject-matter knowledge* refers to the accuracy, cohesiveness, and in-depth subject-matter knowledge of teachers, coherent facts, concepts, and principles in teaching; *curricular knowledge* refers to knowledge of teachers about school district curriculum guides, understanding the scope and sequence of learning goals and objectives, *pedagogical knowledge* refers to teachers effective pedagogical strategies, knowledge to design and organize learning activities for effective learning, and the final indicator is learner knowledge, which refers to teachers' knowledge and understanding of their student's abilities, previous achievements, cultural upbringing, personal interests concerning the subject matter, and emotional and social concerns that interest the students.

On the other hand, the study’s dependent variable is *instructional strategies* (Warnock, 2015) with the following indicators, *instructional strategies*, which refers to teachers' strategy in employing a variety of techniques that can best present the content; *content and expectation* refers to teachers concerned in demonstrating higher order thinking skills, providing in-depth explanations of academic content, the *cognitive challenge* to teacher's questioning strategy that reflects the lesson's substance and goals., stress meaningful concept to connect new knowledge and *questioning* it refers to teaching tips, tricks and methods utilized by teachers to bring about learning.

Fig1 Conceptual Framework Showing the Variables of the Study

Lastly, the mediating variable, which is *employee motivation*, was developed by Nohria, Groysberg, and Lee (2008) that is considered to have a mediating role over the association between professional knowledge and instructional strategy as the mediator with indicators; *basic need* refers to salary increment given to the employee who does their job very well, *safety* refers to the working conditions provided to the employee who feels secure in their job, *esteem* refers to the employee who is satisfied with the responsibility and role in their work, *love* refers to the quality of relationships in the informal workgroup, and *self-actualization* refers to employee realization in his ultimate personal potential.

G. Significance of the Study

This study focused on the mediating effect of employee motivation on the relationship between professional knowledge and teachers' instructional strategies. From a global perspective, a motivated teacher has an extensive understanding of the topic and curriculum areas presented and understands how the subject matter integrates into the educational landscape. Teachers shall be motivated and teach their students the essential knowledge and skills through effective instructional strategies. Though the advancement of knowledge and the advent of technology are present nowadays, having a teacher that values learners as individuals and makes them feel important is of the utmost importance.

Furthermore, the findings benefit the DepEd Officials, for this will be a basis for strengthening the curriculum and other programs that will address the curricular standards and incorporate important content elements. The School Administrators will also benefit from the study to help them design better programs that will implement teachers' use of higher-level thinking skills in teaching instruction and develop the best instructional strategies that will fit into the level of the learners' understanding. Next, the teachers are the study's beneficiaries since the findings will serve as a foundation for connecting current content with previous and future learning experiences, other topic areas, and real-world experiences and applications. Furthermore, teachers who can adapt teaching to accommodate student learning styles regarding their students' perspectives and are receptive to hearing their students' viewpoints

The students will also benefit from this study, for it will serve as a realization that teachers help them to comprehend rather than criticize for their mistakes. Understand the meaning and facts of the content they are learning. Furthermore, parents will appreciate the teacher's endeavors to make the curriculum challenging, significant, and engaging for all students. Lastly, future researchers may obtain information from this study's result for further research and investigation of the mediating effect of employee motivation on the relationship between professional knowledge and teachers' instructional strategies.

H. Definition of Terms

To establish a standard frame of reference, the following terms are defined operationally:

Professional Knowledge refers to the teacher's requisition of an essential understanding of the content and practices for effective teaching (Gess-Newsome, 2018). This study pertains to the teacher's acquisition of practical understanding skills and required skills coupled with the necessary information on the content, curriculum, pedagogy, and learners by study or experiences.

Instructional Strategies refers to several teaching approaches enthusiastically employed by teachers to meet specific learning objectives for particular instruction (Lamon, 2017). This study refers to teachers' tips, tricks, and approaches applied in teaching, typically referring to delivering instruction at their twist and pace to make learning meaningful and fun.

Employee Motivation is an intrinsic or extrinsic push that affects workers' behavior, effort, and organizational performance (Mase, 2021). This study generally means teachers are the driving force to make extraordinary efforts, persistence, and competence in accomplishing any workload, including salary, incentives, recognition, and rewards.

CHAPTER TWO METHODS

This chapter featured the methods and procedures used to gather the necessary data. This comprises the study's data collection process, the research location, the population and sample covering the respondents of the study, the research instrument, and the statistical tools used to analyze the data gathered in the study.

➤ *Research Design*

The study employed a descriptive-correlational quantitative research design to examine the mediating role of employee motivation on the relationship between professional knowledge and instructional strategy. The study adopted a quantitative research method, employing descriptive-correlational design. This quantitative research describes phenomena by collecting numerical data and analyzing it using mathematically based approaches (Creswell, 2014). Meanwhile, Sahin and Mete (2021) defined descriptive design as a style of research that involves collecting data to test hypotheses or respond to queries about the state of the study's issue to gain detailed facts and information on the given topic.

The study used descriptive design since this study seeks to ascertain the condition of the three variables: Instructional Strategies, Professional Knowledge, and Employee Motivation. Since this study also aims to determine how closely interconnected and interdependent the three variables are, a correlational design was adopted. Also, the design is appropriate for determining the preconditions in a mediation analysis study. Meanwhile, Sobel Test was used for mediation analysis by determining the linking effect of the mediator variable (employee motivation) on the relationship between the independent variable (professional knowledge) and dependent variable (instructional strategies). The Sobel test is a subset of the t-test that examines whether the reduction in the effect of the independent variable after incorporating the mediator in the model is statistically significant and whether the mediation effect is statistically significant (Çiçek & Biçer, 2015).

Overall, such types of research design were appropriate in the study since it obtained quantifiable information through a survey questionnaire. This study also determined the correlation of the three variables using mediating analysis. The study gathered data from selected TLE secondary school teachers in the Davao de Oro Division. Data were collected online using Google Forms and undergone appropriate statistical tools in analyzing the data.

➤ *Research Locale*

Presented in Figure 2 is the map of the Philippines highlighting the Research Locale of the study.

The study was conducted in secondary schools under the division of Davao de Oro. Davao de Oro is one of the provinces in the Philippines, specifically located in the Davao Region of Mindanao. It was formerly known as Compostela Valley until December 2019, when a vote adopted a resolution proposing to rename the province to Davao de Oro.

Fig 2 Map of the Philippines Highlighting the Province of Davao De Oro.

The province, otherwise known as ComVal for short, was previously part of Davao del Norte until it was carved out by Republic Act No. 8470, signed by President Fidel V. Ramos on January 30, 1998. Hence then, Davao de Oro is the country's 78th province. It is the Philippines' fourth newest province, behind Zamboanga Sibugay, Dinagat Islands, and Davao Occidental, of which the capital town is Nabunturan due to its central location. The province is bounded to the west by Davao del Norte, to the north by Agusan del Sur, to the east by Davao Oriental, and to the southwest by Davao Gulf.

Davao de Oro was classified as a first-class province based on the 2020 census, and it has 767,547 people living in 11 municipalities with 237 barangays. Moreover, the province of Davao de Oro is divided into two districts, the first and the second district. The 1st district has five municipalities, comprising Municipality of Compostela, Maragusan, Monkayo, Montevista, and New Bataan, while in 2nd district are the municipality of Laak, Nabunturan, Mabini, Maco Mawab, and Pantukan. For the secondary high school, the Davao de Oro division has 60 schools, and for the elementary, 325 schools.

➤ *Population and Sample*

The respondents of the study were the 300 Technology and Livelihood Education (T.L.E.) teachers from Davao de Oro. Slovin formula was used to determine the number of respondents wherein 300 TLE teachers were chosen from 25% of the total population of 1,200 TLE teachers from both Junior and Senior high schools of Davao de Oro Division by stratified random sampling technique. Before conducting the study, the researcher considered the said technique to avoid the researcher's biases and prejudices.

Respondents were given informed consent and permission to participate in the study, and no survey questionnaires were distributed to respondents without their permission. The 300 respondents completed a standardized questionnaire on the mediating effect of employee motivation on the relationship between professional knowledge and teachers' instructional strategies. Due to the division's tight health procedure, the researcher distributed validated questionnaires using Google Forms, and face-to-face engagement was discouraged.

These TLE teachers from the division of Davao de Oro were chosen as the study's respondents because, as observed, professional knowledge assisted teachers with their instructional strategies employing a different mechanism: by improving teacher competence, dedication, or either of these ways that endured in the long run. The researcher also found that teachers are more motivated and effective during the school year, not just in terms of the knowledge they have received but also in how it is transformed into student learning.

However, the school principals, school heads, supervisors, students, teachers on leave, and teachers not teaching T.L.E. were excluded as study respondents. Furthermore, teachers who refused to sign the informed consent form were excluded since the researcher could not study the entire population due to circumstances such as teacher attendance, teachers on leave, and other justifiable reasons that may emerge throughout the study.

A respondent may voluntarily withdraw from any or all of the components of a study in which they agreed to participate at any time. The researcher asked the respondent if they wished to continue participating in the study. If a respondent withdraws from all aspects of the study, the researcher is not permitted to access the respondent's record or any other confidential information for the research.

➤ *Research Instrument*

The study used a validated questionnaire to gather necessary data from the respondents. The professional knowledge consists of 14-item questions from Warnock (2015). The questionnaire had four indicators: subject-matter knowledge, curricular knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, and learners' knowledge, while the instructional strategies questionnaire consists of 19 items used by Warnock (2015), with four indicators: instructional strategies, content expectation, cognitive challenge, and questioning. The mediating variable, employee motivation (Nohria et al., 2008), consists of 20 items with five indicators: basic needs, safety, esteem, love, and self-actualization. Every item was responded to by the respondents on a Likert scale with five points ranging from never to always.

For content validity, the researcher accomplished internal validation. Consultations with research specialists in this field were required. The three-part questionnaire was approved and validated by an expert panel, which received an overall rating of 4.54, considered an excellent validity index. The survey questionnaires were pilot tested among teachers who were not included among the target responders. Cronbach Alpha values for independent, dependent, and mediating factors were 0.935, 0.963, and 0.793, respectively. The findings indicated that the items in the said questionnaires were credible.

The questionnaire was designed in a way the responders may answer it promptly. Thus, the questionnaires utilized the Likert format having a five-point response scale. A Likert Scale is a rating scale in which the subject indicates their agreement or disagreement with a topic. The scales were as follows: always, frequently, occasionally, seldom, and never.

The following range of means with corresponding descriptions was used to describe professional knowledge.

Table 1 Range of Means with Corresponding Descriptions

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	This means that the professional knowledge of teachers is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This means that the professional knowledge of teachers is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This means that the professional knowledge of teachers is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	This means that the professional knowledge of teachers is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means that the professional knowledge of teachers is never manifested.

The five orderable gradations with their respective range of means and descriptions were used to determine the instructional strategies.

Table 2 The Five Orderable Gradations with their Respective Range of Means and Descriptions

Range of Mean	Range of Mean	Range of Mean
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	This means that the instructional strategies of teachers are always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This means that the instructional strategies of teachers are observed oftentimes.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This means that the instructional strategies of teachers are observed sometimes
1.80 – 2.59	Low	This means that the instructional strategies of teachers are rarely observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means that the instructional strategies of teachers are not observed.

In identifying the employee motivation of teachers, the following range of mean with its corresponding descriptions was used.

Table 3 Range of Mean with its Corresponding Descriptions

Range of Mean	Range of Mean	Range of Mean
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	This means that the employee motivation of teachers is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This means that the employee motivation of teachers is observed oftentimes.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This means that the employee motivation of teachers is observed sometimes
1.80 – 2.59	Low	This means that the employee motivation of teachers is rarely observed.
1.00 – 1.7	Very Low	This means that the employee motivation of teachers is not observed.

➤ Data Collection

The researcher followed the following steps and procedures in gathering the necessary data. First, the researcher requested authorization to conduct the study after receiving consent from the panel members. The researcher secured a request letter from the research adviser and a signed endorsement letter from the Dean of the University of Mindanao-Professional. The researcher requested the consent of the study's lead by formal writing to the Schools Division Superintendent's office of the Davao de Oro. The superintendent's endorsement letter was fastened to the letter for the principals of Davao de Oro's secondary schools, requesting permission for the researcher to perform the study.

At that point, the researcher conveyed the survey questionnaires to the respondents to guarantee a 100% poll recovery. A certificate of appearance signed by the school principal was given for documentation. The request form was granted, and the researcher administered the survey form to respondents. All questionnaires were accounted for and retrieved after two days, and within a week, the data were gathered, collated, and tallied for statistical analysis.

For statistical data treatment, the researcher placed the tabulated data of survey responses in an Excel file and then send it to the statistician for analysis. Descriptive statistics, including the mean and standard deviation, were used to determine the level of professional knowledge, instructional strategies, and employee motivation. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to determine the significant association between professional knowledge and instructional strategies, professional knowledge and employee motivation. The considerable influence of professional knowledge on instructional strategies and professional knowledge on employee motivation was determined using multiple regression analysis.

➤ Statistical Tools

The following statistical tools was used to treat the data gathered in the study:

- *Weighted Mean*

This was used to describe the level of professional knowledge, instructional strategies, and employee motivation.

- *Pearson Product –Moment Correlation Coefficient*

This assessed the significant relationship between professional knowledge, instructional strategies, professional knowledge, and employee motivation.

- *Regression Analysis*

This was used to determine the significant influence of the significant relationship between professional knowledge to functional strategies and professional knowledge on employee motivation.

- *Sobel Test*

This was used to examine the mediation effect between an independent variable and a dependent variable with the help of a mediating variable. Also utilized to determine the role of employee motivation in mediating the relationship between professional knowledge and instructional strategies.

- *Mediation Analysis*

Mediation analysis was performed in this study. According to MacKinnon et al. (2002), Mediation analysis is a type of advanced correlational analysis that determines if the effect of one variable on another is transmitted through a third variable. This approach is ideal for this study since it seeks to determine whether professional knowledge substantially affects employee motivation and whether employee motivation, in turn, has a significant influence on instructional strategies.

- *Ethical Consideration*

Ethical guidelines were observed in the conduct of the research. This research firmly adheres to the standards and guidelines the University of Mindanao Ethics Committee set forth. First, the researcher requested a letter of approval from the Davao de Oro's office of the Schools Division Superintendent before conducting and gathering data from the respondents. Then, a consent from the principals of the different schools in the Davao de Oro Division where the study was conducted were secured. There were study protocol assessment criteria to be considered:

- *Voluntary Participation*

The voluntary nature of the study was discussed and emphasized to the respondents. The researcher let the respondents know the risks and benefits of participating in the study. They also have the right to ask anything they find unclear before deciding to participate. The TLE teachers were chosen as the respondents of the study from different secondary schools of the division of Davao de Oro.

However, the school principal, teachers on leave, teachers not teaching TLE and teachers who declined to complete the informed consent form were all excluded from the study. The researcher respects the respondents' decision to participate or not participate in the survey without consequence or penalty.

- *Privacy and Confidentiality*

The researcher respects the rights and privacy of the respondents and ensures that the study adheres to and observes the Data Privacy Act that protects all data being gathered right from the start of the study. The researcher guaranteed that whatever the results of the study at the end, these would not be disclosed to the respondents or any members of the community and would keep the records of the study confidential.

- *Informed Consent Process*

The researcher underwent an informed consent process for this study since it is considered an essential part of research ethics. The researcher gave informed consent to the respondents with their permission. Consent was explained and given to the respondents. This consent was obtained to maintain the confidentiality of the subjects' information. With their permission, survey questionnaires have been sent to respondents.

- *Recruitment*

The researcher utilized the T.L.E teachers in secondary school from the Division of Davao de Oro as the study's respondents, as shown in the population and sample on how the respondents were classified. Also, the manner of data collection, distribution of survey questionnaires, and other procedures are involved in this study.

- *Risks*

The researcher sees to it that the minimization of risk was considered in this study. The researcher firmly adheres to the IATF guidelines against COVID-19 to ensure that the risks and measures in mitigating possible risks was appropriately reviewed. The respondents were protected from physical, psychological, or social economic harm during the study. To avoid ethical violations, the researcher devotes special attention to vulnerable subjects.

- *Benefits*

The result of this study will benefit the Department of Education authorities, school heads, and TLE teachers to develop their cognitive performance and be more driven and motivated to be better teachers in educating students.

- *Plagiarism*

The researcher knew the importance of citing all sources and taking accurate notes. Using and presenting another person's work as your own constitutes plagiarism, especially when done accidentally. Plagiarism is the most common form of research misconduct. When evaluating privileged information for review, such as grants or journal article submissions, the researcher must know that the reading cannot be cited until the work has been published or made accessible to the public. The researcher ensured that the readings in this study underwent paraphrasing to avoid plagiarism issues, no misrepresentation of someone else's work, and that authors of all cited literature were cited properly to ensure research adequacy.

- *Fabrication*

The researcher sees that no fabrication in producing and adding data, observations, or characterizations happened during data collection or experimentation. The researcher ensured that the readings in this study underwent paraphrasing to avoid plagiarism issues, no misrepresentation of someone else's work, and that authors of all cited literature were cited properly to ensure research adequacy.

- *Falsification*

Falsification is the alteration or omission of study findings to support claims, hypotheses, other data, etc. The researcher ensured that no research instrumentation, materials, or methods were manipulated during the study. Manipulating visuals or representations in such a way that distortion of data or reading too much between the lines is also considered a fabrication. To ensure the respondents' safety and welfare, the truthfulness of the results, the adequacy of the research, and the avoidance of conflicts of interest were all rigorously monitored.

- *Conflict of Interest*

These conflicts may involve individual, professional, political, scholarly, or financial interests. The researcher ensured that economic interests did not include employment, research funding, payment for lectures or travel, consultancies, or firm assistance for personnel. The researcher must go beyond what is necessary to guarantee that their conflicts of interest do not affect the methodology or outcome of the research. If uncertain, consult an independent researcher or an Ethics Committee.

- *Deceit*

This study was conducted without a hidden purpose. The researcher did not use deception and protected the respondents from any harm. The study's objective was to determine the mediating effect of employee motivation on the relationship between professional knowledge and teachers' instructional strategies.

- *Permission from the Organization/Location*

The researcher ensured evident adherence to ethical standards and formality of conduct; consequently, a formal letter was addressed to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Davao de Oro division for the study permit. The study was conducted upon the permission given by the authorities.

- *Technology Issues*

The researcher identifies concern as the lack of scientific integrity in educational environments that make substantial use of technology. The researcher ensure that illegal software downloading is not applied in constructing this research. The researcher uses technology appropriately to support the completion of this research paper.

- *Authorship*

As the study's author, the researcher made significant contributions to the intellectual content, including developing and designing the research study and collecting, analyzing, and interpreting the data. The author must attest that the manuscript comprises valid work and assume public responsibility. In particular, the research adviser shall be acknowledged as the study's co-author. The Researcher ensures fair and proper acknowledgment of contributions from the research adviser who has been the co-author and ensures that acknowledgments fully reflect the contributor's input. Finally, as an author, the researcher is typically involved in drafting, reviewing, and approving the submitted manuscript.

CHAPTER THREE RESULTS

The data and the analysis of the results based on the respondents' responses on professional knowledge, instructional strategies, and teacher-employee motivation are established in this chapter. Tables are arranged in the following subheadings: assessment of the level of levels of professional knowledge, instructional strategies, and employee motivation, the correlation between measures, the regression analysis of the mediating effect of employee motivation on the relationship between professional knowledge and instructional strategies of teachers.

➤ *Level of Professional Knowledge*

Table 1 shows the results of the descriptive statistics used to assess TLE teachers' professional knowledge level. Among the indicators, curricular knowledge obtained the highest mean of 4.58, followed by learners' knowledge which obtained the mean of 4.54; next is subject-matter knowledge which obtained the mean of 4.41; and lastly, pedagogical knowledge obtained the lowest mean of 4.37. All indicators have the descriptive equivalent of very high. Taken as a whole, it is inferred that TLE teachers see their professional knowledge in their teaching profession. In addition, the very high levels of all indicators could mean that professional knowledge was always manifested.

Table 4 Level of Professional Knowledge

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Subject-matter Knowledge	0.63	4.41	Very High
Curricular Knowledge	0.57	4.58	Very High
Pedagogical Knowledge	0.67	4.37	Very High
Learners' Knowledge	0.57	4.54	Very High
Overall	0.61	4.48	Very High

The level of professional knowledge perceived by the TLE teachers has an overall mean of 4.48 and is described as very high. The very high level could be attributed to the very high rating given by the respondents in all the indicators. This meant that the respondent's response to the professional knowledge was always manifested. Moreover, it has an SD of 0.61 ($SD < 1.00$), indicating the homogeneity of the responses for this variable.

This implies that professional knowledge, as perceived by the TLE teachers, had a positive conviction about the subject. TLE teachers build interdisciplinary connections across academic areas to engage students in challenging, integrated, and inquisitive learning. In addition, TLE teachers contextualize the competencies from the curriculum guides and set up outlines for lesson plans. Moreover, they create and plan educational activities that allow students of all interests and skill levels to explore the topics, problems, or difficulties. Lastly, they have a deeper understanding of the students as unique individuals concerning their learning capacities, prior accomplishments, cultural background, and personal interests.

This result is parallel to the proposition of Caena (2019) that teachers must be mentors who develop relationships of trust with students, coordinators of both individual and group learning, alchemists who combine strategies, techniques, and resources to inspire students' creativity, welders who join disparate knowledge and activities into a meaningful whole, and team players who are fully aware of and utilize the potential of others as well as themselves. In this way, Teachers acquire a deeper understanding of how to effectively fulfill the needs of the students while enhancing their professional expertise (Persaud, 2018).

According to Schleicher (2018), each teacher possesses enough general knowledge, professional knowledge, competence, and professionalism through continuous active participation in learning actions and activities that help achieve professional development at both personal and organizational levels to serve society further. Teaching quality, student learning results, and teachers' self-actualization are all enhanced due to improved teacher knowledge and competency (Madani, 2019).

Hence, continuous professional development is essential for improving teacher proficiency, professional knowledge, and competence. Teacher competence is attained through continuous learning and development, adapting to changes, assisting with teaching dilemmas, promoting teacher professional knowledge, and expanding teacher functions (Nilsson, 2018). However, there is a consensus on what sorts of learning are substantial for teachers. It is better if the teacher understands what the child thinks. Deliberation of such concerns is addressed by the succeeding information accumulated, which is often an indirect foundation for measuring teacher knowledge (Baumert et al., 2019).

➤ *Level of Instructional Strategies*

Shown in Table 2 is the descriptive statistics results in measuring the level of instructional strategies of TLE Teachers. The indicator that obtained the highest mean of 4.53 is the content expectation, followed by instructional strategies, which obtained the mean of 4.43; next is the cognitive challenge which obtained the mean of 4.41, and questioning obtained the lowest mean of 4.38. All indicators have the descriptive equivalent of very high. The very high level could be attributed to predominantly very high

ratings given by the teachers on instructional strategies of TLE Teachers. In general, it is surmised that TLE teachers were observed to have a commendable instructional strategy for teaching.

The overall mean of instructional strategies is 4.44, assessed to be very high. The very high level could be attributed to results revealing that teachers' instructional strategies are always observed. This meant that the respondents' response to the instructional strategy for teaching was manifested all the time. Moreover, it has an SD of 0.60 (SD <1.00), indicating the homogeneity of the responses for this variable.

This implies that the instructional strategy of TLE teachers is very evident in the subject. TLE teachers link the learning process and results to the real-world and realistic circumstances of the students. Additionally, TLE teachers select the most effective pedagogical techniques and strategies to convey the subject matter. Additionally, they address higher-order concepts and abilities and provide extensive explanations of academic material. Finally, they pose questions that are indicative of the lesson's objectives and sort of information.

Table 5 Level of Instructional Strategies

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Instructional Strategies	0.59	4.43	Very High
Content Expectation	0.59	4.53	Very High
Cognitive Challenge	0.58	4.41	Very High
Questioning	0.62	4.38	Very High
Overall	0.60	4.44	Very High

These results are supported by the study findings of Williams and Williams (2017), that educators can use instructional strategies to make teaching and learning more memorable, meaningful, fun, and enjoyable. The students actively seek opportunities, keeping them on their toes and wanting more than usual. Relevance in the learning process is essential to effective instructional strategies that help build and sustain student engagement methods (Orlich et al., 2017).

Ghosh et al. (2020) also revealed that effective teaching necessitates selecting and implementing appropriate instructional strategies. To be effective, teachers must be able to choose and use appropriate instructional strategies. Making instruction related to real-life problems is a teacher's most effective instructional strategy to boost student learning. This kind of instruction allows students to research, inquire, and actively acquire knowledge about today's significant problems (Angeli & Valanides, 2019).

➤ *Level of Employee Motivation*

Shown in Table 3 are the results of the descriptive statistics on assessing the level of employee motivation as perceived by TLE teachers. Among the indicators, love obtained the highest mean of 4.46, followed by esteem which obtained a mean of 4.37; next is safety which obtained a mean of 4.32; and basic needs, which obtained a mean of 4.20; those indicators obtained a very high level. However, self-actualization obtained the lowest mean of 3.12, which is moderate. The very high-level basic needs, safety, esteem, and love of the employee motivation indicate that the TLE teachers are motivated almost all the time, if not permanently. In addition, the moderate level of self-actualization in the remaining indicator of employee motivation indicates that TLE teachers are seen to carry out their motivation at work most of the time.

The employee motivation obtained an overall mean of 4.09, described as high. The high level could be attributed to the respondents' very high to moderate rating in all the indicators. This meant that the respondent's responses to employee motivation were often observed. Moreover, it has an SD of 0.60 (SD <1.00), indicating the homogeneity of the responses for this variable. This implies that employee motivation is evident. TLE teachers are satisfied with the salary, rest breaks, and leaves given by the department. In addition, the school management encourages teachers to adopt safe practices and use safety equipment. Moreover, they are satisfied with their responsibility and role in work. Teachers also feel more motivated while participating in activities done by the school and the department.

Table 6 Level of Employee Motivation

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Level
Basic Needs	4.20	Very High
Safety	4.32	Very High
Esteem	4.37	Very High
Love	4.46	Very High
Self-actualization	3.12	Moderate
Overall	4.09	High

However, self-actualization garnered the lowest mean, essential in realizing their ultimate personal potential.

These results supported the article of van der Kolk (2018) that the motivation of teachers is less influenced by externally initiated factors such as salary. Money, therefore, influences decisions at every stage. However, some intangibles are the primary motivators for the worker's inspiration to perform effectively. Thus, it is okay for money to improve everyone's drive. The organization must create these policies and procedures, as well as reward systems that are consistent with those policies and procedures, to maximize employee performance. (Locke & Schattke, 2019).

Therefore, Olusadum (2018) stated that it is essential to understand what actually drives employees. Different organizational levels and earning potential may result in individuals with various motivational values. Corporate training can provide employees with opportunities and a sense of obligation to the company, allowing them to work together to repay the reward they received (Nyakundi, 2017). Hence, what inspires people at one organizational level may not inspire others at another. When examining attitudes for motivational purposes, it is possible to distinguish between these values according to economic level and other demographic parameters. (David & Eguzoikpe, 2019).

➤ *Significance of the Relationship between Variables*

Displayed in Table 4 are the results of the relationship between the independent (professional knowledge), dependent (instructional strategies), and mediator (employee motivation) variables. The relationship between the variables was employed using a bivariate Pearson product-moment correlation analysis.

Table 7 Significance of the Relationship between the Variables

Pair	Variables	Correlation Coefficient	p- value	Decision on H_o
IV and DV	Professional Knowledg and Instructional Strategies	.884	0.000	Reject
IV and MV	Professional Knowledge and Employee Motivation	.294	0.000	Reject
MV and DV	Employee Motivation and Instructional Strategies	.334	0.000	Reject

The first zero-ordered correlation analysis between professional knowledge and instructional strategies revealed a computed r-value of 0.884 with a probability value of $p < 0.000$, which is significant at the 0.05 level. This indicates a significant relationship between professional knowledge and instructional strategies. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is therefore rejected.

Similarly, the second bivariate correlation analysis involving professional knowledge and employee motivation response yielded an r-value of 0.294 with a probability value of $p < 0.000$, which is significant at a 0.05 level. This indicates a significant relationship between professional knowledge and employee motivation. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is also rejected.

➤ *Mediation Analysis*

Mediation analysis was conducted to evaluate the mediating effect of employee motivation on the relationship between professional knowledge and instructional strategies. It was hypothesized that professional knowledge would positively predict instructional strategies. Additionally, it was hypothesized that employee motivation would mediate such a relationship. A series of regression analyses were carried out to test these hypotheses.

There are four steps to meet for a third variable to act as a mediator. In Table 5, these are categorized as steps 1 to 4. In step 1, professional knowledge as the independent variable (IV) significantly predicts instructional strategies of TLE teachers is this study's dependent variable (DV). In step 2, professional knowledge significantly predicts employee motivation, the mediator (M). In step 3, employee motivation significantly predicts the instructional strategies of TLE teachers.

Further mediation analysis using a medgraph is necessary to determine the significance of the mediation effect because the three steps (paths a, b, and c) are significant. This analysis involved the Sobel z test. Complete mediation will be attained if the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable ceases to be statistically significant at the conclusion of the analysis. It means the mediator variable mediates all the effects. In addition, if the regression coefficient is substantially reduced at the final step but remains significant, only partial mediation is obtained, which implies that part of the professional knowledge is mediated by employee motivation. Additional components, however, are either direct or mediated by other variables outside the model's scope. In this case, as gleaned in step 4 (denoted as c'), the effect of professional knowledge of instructional strategies was even found to increase after being mediated by employee motivation. With this, partial mediation took place since the effect was found to be significant at $p < 0.05$ level.

Table 8 Regression Results of the Variables in the Four Criteria of the Presence of Mediating Effect

Step	Path	Beta (Unstandardized)	Standard Error	Beta Standardized
Step 1	c	.896	0.027	0.884
Step 2	a	.200	0.038	0.294
Step 3	b	.121	0.042	0.081
Step 4	c'	.872	0.028	0.860

These findings are anchored on the claim of Cheung (2017) that Teachers' professional knowledge had a significant relationship with instructional strategies. The higher the educational attainment of teachers, the better their teaching strategies. Webster-Wright (2019) highlighted that professional growth through which they can acquire professional knowledge develops their instructional strategies in teaching. Knowledgeable teachers are guided in familiarizing themselves with various kinds of teaching strategies that they can use inside the classroom.

These findings are based on existing evidence in the study of Sinclair (2008), which showed a strong correlation between motivational factors and teaching strategies. The experience of teachers plays a vital role in terms of job performance. The motivation of employees is an essential element for the delivery of quality teaching strategies by teachers (Blackmore & Sachs, 2017). Thus, instructional strategies meet the needs of students, and student performance leads to retention (Tehseen & Ul Hadi, 2015).

Moreover, Backfisch et al. (2020) study stated that teachers' professional competence level strongly influences their motivation. Professional competence is the professional knowledge and motivational beliefs that serve as the foundation for mastery of specific professional situations. Both professional knowledge and good motivational prerequisites are essential for teachers (Farjon et al., 2019).

Furthermore, Figure 3 shows the outcome of the computation of mediating effects. At a 0.05 level, the Sobel test resulted in a z-value of 2.527 with a p-value of 0.010886, both of which are significant. This indicates that mediating effect is partial, such that the original direct effect of professional knowledge on instructional strategies improved upon the addition of employee motivation. Sobel Z indicates that adding employee motivation improves the effect of professional knowledge on instructional strategies.

The computed effect size for the mediation test between the three variables is also shown in the figure. The effect size measures how much professional knowledge's effect on instructional strategies can be attributed to the indirect path. The total effect value of 0.896 is the beta of professional knowledge of instructional strategies. The direct effect value of 0.872 is the beta of professional knowledge towards instructional strategies with employee motivation included in the regression. The indirect effect value of 0.200 is the amount of the original beta between the professional knowledge and instructional strategies that now goes through employee motivation to instructional strategies (a * b, where "a" refers to the path between PK and IS and "b" refers to the path between EM and IS).

Fig 3 Medgraph Showing the Variables of the Study

The ratio index is computed by dividing the indirect effect by the total effect; in this case, 0.200 by 0.896 equals 0.223. About 22.3 percent of the total effect of professional knowledge on instructional strategies goes through employee motivation, and about 77.7 percent of the total effect is either direct or mediated by other variables not included in the model.

The result of the study is in line with the opinion stated by Kunter et al. (2013) assertion that teachers are vital actors with strategic roles in school teaching and learning. Moreover, professional competence influences teachers' instructional strategies and motivation. The mastery of their subject field and the ability to manage emotional stability to boost motivation, which can substance academic learning and develop their potential, are indicators of teachers' quality (Wahyuningtyas et al., 2020).

Sumantri and Whardani (2017) also stated that teachers' role in the teaching and learning process is very strategic. The professional competence of a teacher determines the quality of education because it has consequences when they carry out instructional strategies and employees' motivation. Professional competence is a characteristic that distinguishes someone and guides her behavior and thinking in all circumstances; it is long-lasting and can result in the successful performance of one's work, and it frequently manifests itself in one's thoughts, attitudes, and behavior. Teachers' professional competence level can impact their instructional strategies and motivation (Saeid & Eslaminejad, 2016)

CHAPTER FOUR DISCUSSION

This chapter discussed the level of professional knowledge, instructional strategies, and employee motivation. Also contained in this section is the discussion of the correlation between measures and the mediating analysis of employee motivation on the relationship between professional knowledge and instructional strategies.

➤ *Level of Professional Knowledge*

The incredibly high level of professional knowledge means that, as the teacher perceives, it is always manifested. The outcome demonstrates that teachers' professional knowledge meets the standards. They are expected to demonstrate subject matter competence, very high levels of teaching skills, accountability standards, share professional knowledge with their colleagues, care deeply about their students, and possess distinguishing qualities that characterize their effectiveness.

Teachers can choose what to teach and how to teach their students based on a vast range of knowledge at their access. The teacher develops and improves professional knowledge by providing them with many different aspects of professional knowledge. Teachers must regularly train and refresh their knowledge to remain competitive and productive in today's technology-based learning environment. This is comparable to the study of Danielewicz (2021), which refers to teachers' education that does not sufficiently equip them with the essential knowledge and skills necessary for lifelong learning. In order to keep pace, it is possible to continue learning at the end of a degree; rather, the rest of a teacher's life should be an endless effort to learn and develop, Yuan et al., (2017).

However, the findings of previous research in Armour and Yelling (2017) indicate that the process of improving teachers' knowledge and abilities depends on several factors, including the availability of efficient, professional development programs, teachers' availability, readiness to learn and unlearn, teachers' commitment to apply the knowledge and skills acquired, teachers' job satisfaction and motivation, and more (Lovat & Clement, 2018).

Also, Schleicher (2018) stated that a teacher's professional knowledge could shape strategies and guidelines for planning, certification, hiring, and evaluation of the teaching profession. Yuan et al. (2017) indicate that the professional development of teachers is seen to have significant positive correlations with professional knowledge and competence.

The very high curriculum knowledge indicated that the knowledge and abilities required to understand, which incorporates the learning norms or learning objectives, should likely meet. The teacher's familiarity with lessons and scholarly content taught in school or a specific subject area is necessary for the teaching process (Madani, 2019). Curriculum knowledge includes the lesson instructions, the assignments, and the tasks given. In other words, curriculum refers to the precise learning objectives, activities, tasks, and resources used to teach a course (Lokshyna, 2018).

This is contrary to what was espoused by Niemela and Tirri (2018) that the change in curriculum integration is currently demanding. Teachers who specialize in teaching one or a few subjects are increasingly expected to connect various courses to generate possibilities for integrated learning (Chan & Hume, 2019).

Furthermore, Deng (2018) stated that teachers have a very high sense of learners' knowledge, manifested in terms of the unique skills each learner displays in the classroom to target teaching toward students' learning needs effectively. They also believe that they are well knowledgeable of what exactly is expected of them, despite substantial efforts at enhancing students' skills being least studied how teachers' knowledge of individual students' skills plays an essential role in instruction and learning (Wang et al., 2022).

This was in the study of Boyle et al. (2018), which revealed that teachers' awareness of students' prior knowledge is hard to gauge. To facilitate students learning, teachers should consistently build up professional knowledge of practice. Good teaching entails skills, knowledge, and abilities. It makes sense that such knowledge demands to be perceived, created, and developed (Efu, 2020).

Wang et al. (2022) teachers also fared a very high sense of subject-matter knowledge in their work field, which is attested in terms of having these measures identified with teacher's knowledge of subjects they teach; they are just intermediary factors and do not directly test teacher's comprehension of the specific concepts, facts, and skills that they are expected to possess. The teachers may have sensed a high feeling of a complex device for estimating subject matter knowledge and utilized this instrument in a more extensive report (Guerriero, 2017).

The statements are inimical to what was espoused by Sadler et al. (2018), that teacher's subject matter knowledge is expectedly needed to teach a course for age level while No Child Left Behind unleashed an unparalleled test of students' knowledge, there has been moderately insignificant assessment to candidly gauge. The teacher's content knowledge is very

significant in enhancing teaching and learning. It provided the necessary information and found that teachers' knowledge influences student learning (Voogt et al., 2017).

Also, according to Gan et al. (2022), the very high level of pedagogical knowledge indicates professional knowledge that has been included, such as their knowledge and speculations, just as the school's policies encompassed how teaching may and may not be done. Likewise, it embodies how teachers make the topic more understandable using comparisons, illustrations, designs, demonstrations, and other teaching procedures. Practice is where pedagogical subject understanding is developed. Nevertheless, there are other places where one can learn about effective instructional representations. Most teachers acquire their professional knowledge via instruction (Boyle et al., 2018).

Consequently, Gess-Newsome (2018) discussed that pedagogical content knowledge has more impact on student achievement than content knowledge alone. Understanding teachers' knowledge is a multifaceted issue that involves recognizing essential core elements in teaching and learning, the notion of knowledge, and how teachers' knowledge is implemented in the classroom. Furthermore, pedagogical knowledge is the mixing of content and how it is instructed in teachers' conviction as educators (Guerriero, 2017).

In like manner, each teacher possesses enough general knowledge, professional knowledge, competence, and professionalism through continuous active involvement in learning actions and activities that help achieve professional development at both personal and organizational levels to serve society further. The level of teacher competence could be achieved through constant learning and development, adapting to changes, helping deal with teaching dilemmas, promoting professional knowledge, and building up the diversity of teacher roles (Lovat & Clement, 2018).

➤ *Level of Instructional Strategies*

There is a very high level of instructional strategies of teachers, and it is manifested all the time. This is because of the very high ratings given to instructional strategies, content and expectation, cognitive challenge, and questioning. The result shows that the mechanism in introducing great content serves as the how of presentation that gives corresponding importance to what to present, providing a latch onto content bundled fascinatingly and engagingly. Different methods are the fundamental factors in learning, and an appropriate teaching strategy is necessary for effective instruction.

This is correlated to what Morrison et al. (2019) espoused that teachers are equipped with flexibility essential in addressing the individual needs and differences of the learners. Instructional strategies approach available to the educator in the teaching and learning more memorable, meaningful, fun, and enjoyable. The learners engage actively for opportunities on their toes and want more than usual (Williams & Williams, 2017). This type of instruction enables individuals to investigate, question, and purposefully build knowledge of actual issues that are pertinent to their daily lives, according to Angeli and Valanides (2019). Moreover, when learning is authentic, especially when real-world tasks have individualized outcomes, students are more motivated and engaged.

Further, Kember and Kwan (2020) claim that the academic goals of all students are the foundation of instructional practices, and they take precedence over other variables in the classroom. Teachers must be educated about the material and the correct teaching methods to help students achieve their learning objectives (Zhan et al., 2022).

Moreover, Wagner (2019) stated that the very high level of content expectation is indicative that the best way to improve instruction is to develop teachers' content knowledge, ending up with sophisticated levels of knowledge, and utilize a repertoire of instructional methods, strategies, and approaches that continually cultivated to convey that material (Smart & Marshall, 2018).

Thus, Weimer (2018) stated that the best teachers are not among those who have the most sophisticated content knowledge. Instead, the best teachers use various teaching techniques, including those that use technology, and modify the learning environment to meet the unique needs of each student (Lamon, 2017).

Consequently, a very high level was seen in teachers' instructional strategies, which indicates that they are firmly established in each student's academic objectives, which take precedence over other classroom dynamics.

According to Monsivais (2020), it says that the demands in teaching effectively, teachers need to have a basic understanding of how to plan, coordinate, and use their attributes, goals, and skills while creating lessons, delivering them, and assessing their effectiveness. Moreover, throughout the development of teachers' instructional materials, it is positively influenced by cognitive skills. Depending on the method of instruction, motivation, excitement, retention, interest, and applicable learning may vary (Wagner, 2019).

Lastly, students learn to reason, guess, invent, solve issues, and connect ideas with their applications by using questioning, which is a technique used by teachers to help students collaborate, rely more on themselves to determine whether something is correct, and learn to do so (Smart & Marshall, 2018). Prepared questions will help to engage students in meaningful ways.

Students are expected to reference textual evidence and make inferences to support their conclusions. They must learn to ask and respond to metacognitive inquiries that advance their learning. (Sasson et al., 2018).

This is like Tsiplakides and Keramida's (2019) assertion that teachers must modify their instructional strategies for all students to learn at high levels to create a student-centered learning culture. They educate students on how to direct their work successfully and when and how to lend a hand to one another. Content equally matters with the process. When instruction promotes meaningful conceptualization, especially when it highlights students' understanding of the world, students achieve higher (Angeli & Valanides, 2019).

➤ *Level of Employee Motivation*

The level of motivation displayed by the TLE teachers is high, obtained based on the respondents' responses in love, esteem, safety, basic needs, and self-actualization. Teachers are inspired to work more productively when they see someone who cares about and values their work.

This is related to the point of view of David and Eguzoikpe (2019) that it works as a vehicle's steering wheel that directs one's activities. In this view, motivation is abstract since various strategies produce different results at different times, and no single strategy can consistently generate guaranteed favorable results. Teacher motivation is essential in promoting teaching and learning excellence (Nyakundi, 2017).

Hanaysha (2019) stated that rewards are essential to employee motivation. Internal benefits, such as autonomy and the joy of completing a task, are intrinsic rewards. Extrinsic rewards, on the other hand, are material rewards like pay, bonuses, ancillary benefits, and promotions. An efficient incentive program should be based on productivity to keep top performers in the organization (Nyakundi, 2017).

On the other hand, Locke and Schattke (2019) claimed that excessive levels of job stress, burnout, and discontent might have a negative impact on motivation and job performance. Inadequate pay, a poor career structure, few opportunities for advancement, inadequate school facilities, an insufficient school disciplinary policy, the school head, and other teachers' attitudes and behavior, students' poor work attitudes, and lack of interest in school are all factors in students' dissatisfaction with school authorities (van der Kolk, 2018).

Similarly, the TLE teachers have a very high level of basic needs. Their love, sense of belonging, and psychological needs can be a model for this. These findings align with what Cummings and Worley (2019) have suggested when a teacher takes care of themselves physically and is prepared to share it with other people like family or friends. Teachers' motivation is less affected by elements that are begun externally, like salary. The department must create these policies and procedures, as well as reward systems that are consistent with those policies and procedures, in order to maximize employee performance (Schattke, 2019).

Moreover, all factors that affect employees' safety, health, and well-being are covered by workplace safety. It has been found that they are comfortable with the fact that there are effective workplace safety programs that often significantly impact the school's bottom line. It is consistent with the findings of Christian et al. (2019), who stated that workplace safety encompasses workers' security, health, and well-being. This can include environmental dangers, hazardous working conditions or processes, drug and alcohol addiction, and workplace violence. Employee retention and productivity gains are equipped with effective workplace safety regulations (Tamers et al., 2020).

Also, TLE teachers' very high self-esteem indicates that they have excellent or negative self-evaluations, as expressed in how we feel about it. Furthermore, Moksnes and Espnes (2018) asserted that self-esteem is appealing as a social psychology construct because it influences specific outcomes such as academic achievement, happiness, marital and relationship satisfaction, and criminal behavior.

This presumed that to attain high clientele satisfaction, teachers and staff needed to provide a reliable service and decrease unreliable service to clients. Consequently, most organizations are likely to include. It has been found that many organizations need to recognize the obvious fact that an organization is made up entirely of people. Furthermore, the truth is that people are motivated by love (Perfilyeva, 2019).

Lastly, it was found that TLE teachers tend to exhibit a moderate level of self-actualization. Their passions, originality, drive for growth, and capacity for responsibility and independence exemplify this. This is fundamentally similar to the philosophy of self-actualization, which emphasizes doing inner work to understand one's strengths, interests, goals, and activities (Perfilyeva, 2019).

As a result, TLE teachers must be driven and more likely to inspire students to learn in the classroom to ensure the implementation of educational innovations and feelings of pleasure and fulfillment (Nyakundi, 2017). In addition, adequate acknowledgment can boost teachers' enthusiasm and productivity, resulting in increased organizational performance (Hanaysha, 2019).

➤ *Correlation between Professional Knowledge, Instructional Strategies and Employee Motivation*

The relationship between the variables of professional knowledge, teacher's instructional strategies, and employee motivation was revealed using a bivariate correlation analysis utilizing Pearson product-moment correlation. Professional knowledge was positive and strongly associated with the instructional strategies of teachers. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is thereby rejected. Professional knowledge and employee motivation also reject the null hypothesis of no significant relationship exists between the variables. Moreover, the third pair, employee motivation and instructional strategies of teachers, also reject the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the variables mentioned.

To begin, professional knowledge has a positive and significant relationship with teachers' instructional strategies. This implies that the better the teaching strategies, the higher the teachers' educational attainment. This is consistent with Cheung's (2017) study, which found that professional knowledge gained through educational attainment and several years of teaching experience is related to the extent to which different teaching strategies are used.

Teachers' professional knowledge interplays their competence in harnessing suitable instructional strategies in teaching their learners. Meanwhile, teachers' expertise is being challenged in the wise selection of instructional strategies by considering their variation and appropriateness, content and expectation, cognitive challenge, and mode of delivering instruction that suits learners' needs and individual differences (Kunter et al., 2018).

Similarly, professional knowledge positively and significantly relates to employee motivation. This implies a strong link between professional knowledge and teachers' motivation. The study's findings correlate with the pronouncements of Gitonga (2017), who mentioned that developing professional knowledge and abilities, center competencies, educational resources, and techniques that determine academic success and performance all depend on motivation.

Consequently, Richardson and Watt (2018) noted that realizing higher-order needs, the foundation of genuine professional happiness is feasible. It was also stated that if the teacher wants reasonable pay that addresses their professional knowledge, it will positively impact their drive to engage in professional development activities and their motivation to carry out teaching assignments well.

Teachers' motivation plays a vital role in the delivery of quality instructional strategies of teachers. For this reason, they must understand that, in improving student achievement, quality of instruction is essential. Since the principal is the school's educational leader, they must assess teachers working knowledge and motivation about effective instructional strategies (Blackmore & Sachs, 2017).

Lastly, employee motivation significantly relates to their instructional strategies for teaching. This implies that teacher motivation is essential to enhancing teaching strategies and effectiveness. This parallels the pronouncements of Alibakhshi et al. (2020), stating that teaching techniques, practices, and instructional behaviors concerning teacher motivation variables have all been explored regarding teaching effectiveness.

➤ *Mediating Effect of Employee Motivation on the Relationship between Professional Knowledge and Instructional Strategies*

For mediation analysis to be carried out, a series of regression procedures were conducted. Based on the results, professional knowledge significantly predicts teachers' instructional strategies. This is inimical to the findings of Reigeluth (1999), who averred that the teachers' professional knowledge predicts their instructional strategies. It indicates how teachers' professional knowledge is imparted to engage in interaction appropriate for the promotion of instruction or acquisition the knowledge (Heneman & Schwab, 1972).

Teachers' professional knowledge has also been considered an important psychological aspect of instructional strategies. Moreover, knowledgeable Teachers are guided in familiarizing various kinds of teaching strategies that they can use inside the classroom. Further, Webster-Wright (2019) stated that professional knowledge helps develop instructional strategies in teaching. Stronge (2018), Cheung (2017), and Webster-Wright (2019) studies similarly agreed on the fact that professional knowledge is essential in the utilization of instructional strategy.

In the same way, professional knowledge significantly predicts employee motivation. This finding parallels the study of Richardson and Watt (2018), whose results show that teachers want fair compensation that considers their specialized skills, which will positively affect their motivation to perform teaching assignments adequately and their interest in engaging in professional development activities. The growth of professional knowledge and abilities, center competencies, educational resources, and techniques determining academic success and performance depend on motivation (Gitonga, 2017).

Consequently, employee motivation significantly predicts the instructional strategies of the teachers. In connection, Toropova et al. (2021) state that teachers' motivation predicts the teaching strategies of teachers. The satisfaction and enjoyment of teachers at work hinder them from wanting to learn new things and enhance their teaching methods. Teachers' motivation is necessary to deliver effective instructional strategies (Blackmore & Sachs, 2017).

Lastly, it was found that employee motivation mediates the original direct effect of professional knowledge on the teachers' instructional strategies. This implies that a partial mediation was achieved, which means that professional knowledge's impact on teachers' instruction strategies is not reduced but slightly enhanced when employee motivation is included. This was like the idea of Blackmore and Sachs (2017) that motivated and knowledgeable teachers could serve as initiators, facilitators, managers, and advocates of the importance of quality to improved instructional strategies.

For this reason, a greater understanding of how employee motivation significantly mediates the relationship between professional knowledge and teachers' instructional strategies is crucial because it can affect the performance of TLE teachers, which impacts the students.

Further, the researcher stated that employee motivation is always evident to those who are professionally knowledgeable and can develop an instructional strategy for teaching. With this current proposition, TLE teachers who are highly knowledgeable about their work are motivated, impacting their teaching instructional strategies.

➤ *Conclusion*

In this section, conclusions are drawn after considering the study's findings. The respondents, TLE teachers in the Division of Davao de Oro, perceived very high levels of professional knowledge, instructional strategies in teaching, and a high level of employee motivation. The findings also support a significant relationship between TLE teachers' professional knowledge and instructional strategies.

Similarly, there is a strong link between professional knowledge and employee motivation. A solid association exists between professional knowledge and teachers' instructional strategies, indicating that the two variables have a significant relationship. Furthermore, the study suggests that employee motivation significantly mediates the relationship between professional knowledge and teachers' instructional strategies.

Finally, the findings supported Reigeluth's (1999) instructional theory, Heneman and Schwab's (1972) expectancy theory, Stronge's (2018) proposition, and Webster-Wright's (2019) and Gitonga's (2017) pronouncements. As a result, employee motivation is essential in mediating the relationship between professional knowledge and teachers' instructional strategies. The preceding propositions discuss the relationship between the variables used in the study. Thus, these propositions are parallel in the current study because it concerns the mediating effect of employee motivation on the relationship between teachers' professional knowledge and instructional strategies.

➤ *Recommendations*

The study discovered a significant relationship between teachers' professional knowledge and instructional strategies. As a result, the researcher recommends that the superintendent of the school's division continue the leadership practices and encourage all teachers to pursue postgraduate studies to maintain the division's TLE teachers' very high level of professional knowledge and instructional strategies.

The study also revealed a significant relationship between teachers' professional knowledge and instructional strategies. As a result, the researcher suggests that the school's division superintendent continue to support teachers who are pursuing master's and doctorate degrees, as well as organize training and seminars on the discourse of instructional strategies related to the subject of TLE for teachers to maintain a very high level of professional knowledge and instructional strategies.

The researcher also recommends future studies related to this study in different fields, such as Mathematics and Social Studies. Future research for developing intervention programs is needed to identify the factors that could improve professional knowledge and employee motivation to develop the instructional strategies of TLE.

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Appendix A

Research Instrument

THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDGE AND INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES OF TEACHERS

Name (Optional): _____ School: _____

Direction: Kindly answer the following items by putting a check (/) on the column that corresponds to your answer using the following scale.

Rating	Descriptive	Interpretation
5	Always	This means that the item embodied in the statement is always manifested.
4	Often	This means that the item embodied in the statement is manifested most often.
3	Sometimes	This means that the item embodied in the statement is manifested in few instances.
2	Seldom	This means that the item embodied in the statement is seldom.
1	Never	This means that the item embodied in the statement is not manifested at all.

Part I: Professional Knowledge

	Always	Often	Sometimes	Seldom	Never
Subject-matter Knowledge <i>In our school, as a teacher I/ I am ...</i>					
1. have accurate, cohesive, and in-depth subject-matter knowledge.					
2. possess a coherent body of knowledge about the facts, concepts, principles, methodology, and important generalization of the subject areas taught					
3. make interdisciplinary connections across subject areas to engage students in challenging, integrated, and exploratory learning.					
Curricular Knowledge <i>In our school, as a teacher I/ I am ...</i>					
1. know and understand the curriculum guide and standards set by the Department of Education.					
2. understand the scope and sequence of learning goals and objectives.					
3. develop appropriate lessons base on the curriculum guide competencies and set up outlines for lesson planning.					
4. able to contextualize lessons to achieve the curriculum guide competencies, content standard and performance standard.					

Pedagogical Knowledge <i>In our school, as a teacher I/ I am ...</i>	Always	Often	Sometimes	Seldom	Never
1. choose the most effective pedagogical strategies that can best communicate subject content.					
2. design and organize learning activities that are appropriate for learners of different interests and abilities to explore the topics, problems, or issues.					
3. exhibit instructional practices that are supported by current research.					
Learner Knowledge <i>In our school, as a teacher I/ I am ...</i>	Always	Often	Sometimes	Seldom	Never
1. understand the learning needs of learners especially with special needs.					
2. relate subject matter to the personal and social concerns that appeal to the learners.					
3. know students as individuals regarding their learning abilities, prior achievement, cultural background, and personal interests.					
4. anticipate the conceptions, misconceptions, and possible difficulties the students are likely to have when learning content area.					

Teacher Self-Assessment Checklist
Part II: Instructional Strategies

Instructional strategies <i>In our school, as a teacher I/ I am ...</i>	Always	Often	Sometimes	Seldom	Never
1. employ a variety of techniques and instructional strategies to enhance student motivation and decrease discipline problems.					
2. use both direct instruction and indirect instruction flexibly to serve appropriate learning purposes.					
3. stresses meaningful conceptualization, emphasizing the students’ own knowledge of the world.					
4. match instruction on students’ achievement levels and needs.					
5. think through likely misconceptions that may occur during instruction and monitor students for these misconceptions.					
6. connect the learning process and outcomes to the authentic contexts in students’ real life.					
7. adjust the delivery and pacing of the lesson in response to student cues.					
Content and Expectation <i>In our school, as a teacher I/ I am ...</i>	Always	Often	Sometimes	Seldom	Never
1. choose appropriate pedagogical strategies that can best present the content.					
2. give clear examples and offer guided practice.					
3. make the learning student-centered.					
4. stresses student responsibility and accountability in mastery of content and skills.					
5. teach students to reflect on learning progress.					
Cognitive Challenge <i>In our school, as a teacher I/ I am ...</i>	Always	Often	Sometimes	Seldom	Never

1. concerned with having students learn and demonstrate higher order thinking skills rather than memorization of facts.					
2. provide in-depth explanations of academic content and cover higher-order concepts and skills thoroughly.					
3. stresses meaningful concept mapping to connect new knowledge with prior learning.					
Questioning <i>In our school, as a teacher I/ I am ...</i>	Always	Often	Sometimes	Seldom	Never
1. ask questions that reflect type of content and goals of the lesson.					
2. ask questions of varying depths of knowledge.					
3. use wait time during questioning.					
4. recognize the pattern in student learning and promptly adjust instruction to maximize student learning.					

Part III: Employee Motivation

Direction: Please answer the following items by putting a check (/) on the column that corresponds to your answer using the following scale.

Rating	Descriptive	Interpretation
	Strongly Agree	This means that the item embodied in the statement is evident at all times.
4	Agree	This means that the item embodied in the statement is evident oftentimes.
3	Neither agree nor disagree	This means that the item embodied in the statement is either evident
2	Disagree	This means that the item embodied in the statement is seldom evident.
1	Strongly Disagree	This means that the item embodied is not evident at all.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Basic Needs					
1. Salary increments given to me to do my job very well really motivates me.					
2. Financial incentives motivates me more than non-financial incentives					
3. I am satisfied with the salary I draw at present.					
4. I am satisfied with the lunch break, rest breaks and leaves given by the department.					
Safety					
1. Good physical working conditions are provided by the department					
2. The Department ensure that employees are working in a safe environment.					

3. The Department encourage employees to adopt safe practices and safety equipment.					
4. The medical benefits provided in the department are satisfactory.					
Esteem	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither agree nor	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1. Visibility with head management is important to me.					
2. I feel that my head always recognize the work done by me.					
3. I feel that job I do gives me a good status					
4. I am satisfied with the responsibility and role that I have in my work.					
Love	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither agree nor	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1. The quality of the relationship in my colleagues is quite important to me.					
2. I am satisfied with the support from my head and the department.					
3. I feel a fair amount of team spirit.					
4. I feel more motivated while participating in activities done by the school and the department.					
Self-Actualization	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither agree nor	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I want to be best at my own job.					
I generally like to schedule my own work and to make job-related decisions with a minimum of supervision.					
I find opportunities for advancement in this department.					
I am for self-knowledge and enlightenment. The most important thing to me is realizing ultimate personal potential.					

Appendix B

Letter to Conduct the Study

Professional Schools
Ground Floor, Ps Building
Matina, Davao City
Telephone: (082)305-0645 Local 189

September 28, 2021

DR. EUFEMIA T. GAMUTIN, CESO V
School Division Superintendent
Division of Davao de Oro

Dear Ma'am:

The undersigned is currently working on her thesis, **"The Mediating effect of Employee Motivation on the relationship between Professional Knowledge and Instructional Strategies"** as a requirement for the degree of **Master of Arts in Education Major in Technology and Livelihood Education**.

In this regard, the researcher would like to request your approval to conduct the study in your area of responsibility and the confidentiality of the data that you will share will be carefully safeguarded. Attached herewith is a sample of the interview guide/survey questionnaire that reflects the topics and questions to be discussed.

Looking forward for your favorable response on the said request.

Respectfully yours,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Juvie O. Bangcasan'.

JUVIE O. BANGCASAN
Researcher
09996070084

Noted by:

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Liezel V. Chan'.

LIEZEL V. CHAN, Ph.D.
Research Adviser

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Eugenio S. Guhao, Jr.'.

EUGENIO S. GUHAO, JR., DM
Dean, Professional School

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
REGION XI
SCHOOLS DIVISION OF DAVAO DE ORO

**Office of the Schools Division
Superintendent**

October 15, 2021

JUVIE O. BANGCASAN
Researcher
University of Mindanao
Matina, Davao City

Dear Ms. Bangcasan:

This has reference to your letter requesting permission to conduct a study to the selected public schools in Davao de Oro Division to gather data for your Thesis entitled "The Mediating Effect of Employee Motivation on the Relationship Between Professional Knowledge and Instructional Strategies".

It is informed that this Office interposes no objection to your request provided that the following requirements are properly complied with, to wit:

1. The endeavor shall be consulted with the Section Head/ School Head of the school where you intend to conduct your study at least two weeks ahead to ensure that no classes/activities will be disrupted;
2. Strict adherence to the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) COVID- 19 protocols and health guidelines as implemented by this Office;
3. No instructional time shall be utilized for the purpose;
4. An Action Research shall be conducted as an upshot of this study;
5. The results and recommendations shall be submitted in hardcopy immediately and to be discussed with the school head concerned for consideration on their plan of action.

It is advised that a copy of the research study in its final form shall be submitted to this Office upon completion.

SS

Truly yours,

EUFEMIA T. GAMUTIN, CESO V
Schools Division Superintendent

PN: 10152021-172

Capitol Complex, Cabidanan, Nabunturan, Davao de Oro
website: www.depeddavaodeoro.ph • email ad: davaodeoro@deped.gov.ph • cp#: +639513871728
PIONEERING in Instructional Innovations PROPAGATING Universal Values PRODUCING Globally Competent Graduates
Code: SDO-CV-OSDS-016 Revision: 4 Effectivity: May 27, 2020

APPENDIX C

LETTERS TO THE EVALUATORS

September 27, 2021

DR. ELDEN D. ORBETA
Education Program Supervisor
Department of Education
Division of Panabo City

Sir:

Pleasant Day!

The undersigned is currently conducting a research entitled, "**THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDGE AND INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES**" as a requirement for the degree of Master of Arts in Education Major in Technology and Livelihood Education (T.L.E.)

With this matter, I humbly ask your expertise and assistance for the validation of the questionnaire. Further, it would be appreciated if you could write your comments and suggestions of the above-mentioned questionnaire.

Thank you very much and to God be the glory.

Very truly yours,

JUVIE O. BANGCASAN
Researcher

Noted:

DR. LIEZEL V. CHAN
Adviser

June 23, 2021

MYLA N. MASCARIÑAS, MAED

Faculty
UM Professional School
Matina, Davao City

Madam:

Pleasant Day!

The undersigned is currently conducting a research entitled, **“THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDGE AND INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES”** as a requirement for the degree of Master of Arts in Education Major in Technology and Livelihood Education (T.L.E.)

With this matter, I humbly ask your expertise and assistance for the validation of the questionnaire. Further, it would be appreciated if you could write your comments and suggestions of the above-mentioned questionnaire.

Thank you very much and to God be the glory.

Very truly yours,

JUVIE O. BANGCASAN
Researcher

Noted:

DR. LIEZEL V. CHAN
Adviser

June 23, 2021

DR. JOCELYN B. BACASMOT

PHO Applied Linguistics
UM Professional School
Matina, Davao City

Madam:

Pleasant Day!

The undersigned is currently conducting a research entitled, **“THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDGE AND INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES”** as a requirement for the degree of Master of Arts in Education Major in Technology and Livelihood Education (T.L.E.)

With this matter, I humbly ask your expertise and assistance for the validation of the questionnaire. Further, it would be appreciated if you could write your comments and suggestions of the above-mentioned questionnaire.

Thank you very much and to God be the glory.

Very truly yours,

JUVIE O. BANGCSAN
Researcher

Noted:

DR. LIEZEL V. CHAN
Adviser

June 23, 2021

DR. LAILANIE TINGSON
Professor
UM Professional School
Matina, Davao City

Madam:

Pleasant Day!

The undersigned is currently conducting a research entitled, **“THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDGE AND INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES”** as a requirement for the degree of Master of Arts in Education Major in Technology and Livelihood Education (T.L.E.)

With this matter, I humbly ask your expertise and assistance for the validation of the questionnaire. Further, it would be appreciated if you could write your comments and suggestions of the above-mentioned questionnaire.

Thank you very much and to God be the glory.

Very truly yours,

JUVIE O. BANGCASAN
Researcher

Noted:

DR. LIEZEL V. CHAN
Adviser

June 23, 2021

DR. MARY ANN E. TARUSAN
Professor
UM Professional School
Matina, Davao City

Madam:

Pleasant Day!

The undersigned is currently conducting a research entitled, "**THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDGE AND INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES**" as a requirement for the degree of Master of Arts in Education Major in Technology and Livelihood Education (T.L.E.)

With this matter, I humbly ask your expertise and assistance for the validation of the questionnaire. Further, it would be appreciated if you could write your comments and suggestions of the above-mentioned questionnaire.

Thank you very much and to God be the glory.

Very truly yours,

JUVIE O. BANGCASAN
Researcher

Noted:

DR. LIEZEL V. CHAN
Adviser

APPENDIX D

VALIDATION SHEET FOR RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRES

 The University of Mindanao	<h2 style="margin:0;">PROFESSIONAL SCHOOLS</h2> [<input type="checkbox"/>] Main [<input type="checkbox"/>] Branch _____				
VALIDATION SHEET FOR RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE					
Name of Evaluator : <u>Myla Mae N. Mascariñas</u> Degree : <u>MAED – H.E.</u> Position : <u>Faculty Member</u> Number of Years of Teaching : _____ To the Evaluator : _____ ratings Points of Equivalent : _____	Please check the appropriate box for your 5 - Excellent 2 - Fair 4 - Very Good 1 - Poor 3 - Good				
ITEMS	5	4	3	2	1
1. Clarity of Directions and Items The vocabulary level, language, structure and conceptual level of questions suit the level of participants. The directions and the items are written in a clear and simple language.	/				
2. Presentation and Organization of Items The items are presented and organized in logical manner.	/				
3. Suitability of Items The Item is appropriate and represents the substance of the research. The questions are designed to determine the conditions, knowledge, perception and attitudes that are supposed to be measured.		/			
4. Adequateness of Items per Category or Indicator The items represent the coverage of research adequately. The questions per area category are adequate representations of all the questions needed for research.		/			
5. Attainment of Purpose The instrument fulfills the objectives for which it was constructed.	/				
6. Objectivity Each item questions only one specific answer or measures only one behavior and no aspect of the questionnaire is a suggestion of the researcher.	/				
7. Scale and Evaluation Rating Scale The scale adapted is appropriate for the items.	/				
Title of Approved Research: <u>THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDGE AND INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES</u>					
Name of Researcher: <u>JUVIE BANGCASAN</u> Research Adviser: _____ Date of Evaluation of the Questionnaire: _____					
Remarks of the Evaluator: Go over with the questionnaire and check the inserted marginal notes. I also find 2 items inappropriate under Part 3 - Safety					
 MYLA MAE N. MASCARINAS Signature Above Printed Name					
F-13550-011/ Rev. # 3/ Effectivity: January 25, 2018					

	[] Main [/] Branch PANABO _____ VALIDATION SHEET FOR RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE																																																
Name of Evaluator : _____ Degree : _____ Position : _____ Number of Years of Teaching : _____ To the Evaluator : _____ Points of Equivalent : _____	DR. JOCELYN B. BACASMOT _____ MS, MAED, PhD _____ Dean _____ 27 _____ Please check the appropriate box for your ratings 5 - Excellent 2 - Fair 4 - Very Good 1 - Poor 3 - Good																																																
<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 60%;">ITEMS</th> <th style="width: 5%;">5</th> <th style="width: 5%;">4</th> <th style="width: 5%;">3</th> <th style="width: 5%;">2</th> <th style="width: 5%;">1</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td> 1. Clarity of Directions and Items The vocabulary level, language, structure and conceptual level of questions suit the level of participants. The directions and the items are written in a clear and simple language. </td> <td style="text-align: center;">/</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td> 2. Presentation and Organization of Items The items are presented and organized in logical manner. </td> <td style="text-align: center;">/</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td> 3. Suitability of Items The Item is appropriate and represents the substance of the research. The questions are designed to determine the conditions, knowledge, perception and attitudes that are supposed to be measured. </td> <td style="text-align: center;">/</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td> 4. Adequateness of Items per Category or Indicator The items represent the coverage of research adequately. The questions per area category are adequate representations of all the questions needed for research. </td> <td style="text-align: center;">/</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td> 5. Attainment of Purpose The instrument fulfills the objectives for which it was constructed. </td> <td style="text-align: center;">/</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td> 6. Objectivity Each item questions only one specific answer or measures only one behavior and no aspect of the questionnaire is a suggestion of the researcher. </td> <td style="text-align: center;">/</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td> 7. Scale and Evaluation Rating Scale The scale adapted is appropriate for the items. </td> <td style="text-align: center;">/</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	ITEMS	5	4	3	2	1	1. Clarity of Directions and Items The vocabulary level, language, structure and conceptual level of questions suit the level of participants. The directions and the items are written in a clear and simple language.	/					2. Presentation and Organization of Items The items are presented and organized in logical manner.	/					3. Suitability of Items The Item is appropriate and represents the substance of the research. The questions are designed to determine the conditions, knowledge, perception and attitudes that are supposed to be measured.	/					4. Adequateness of Items per Category or Indicator The items represent the coverage of research adequately. The questions per area category are adequate representations of all the questions needed for research.	/					5. Attainment of Purpose The instrument fulfills the objectives for which it was constructed.	/					6. Objectivity Each item questions only one specific answer or measures only one behavior and no aspect of the questionnaire is a suggestion of the researcher.	/					7. Scale and Evaluation Rating Scale The scale adapted is appropriate for the items.	/					
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Title of Approved Research: THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDGE AND INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES																																																	
Name of Researcher: <u>JUVIE O. BANGCASN</u>																																																	
Research Adviser: <u>DR. LIEZEL CHAN</u>																																																	
Date of Evaluation of the Questionnaire: <u>July 21, 2021</u>																																																	
Remarks of the Evaluator: <u>Approved for administration</u>																																																	
 JOCELYN B. BACASMOT Signature Above Printed Name																																																	

<b style="font-size: 2em; color: red;">UM The University of Mindanao	<h2 style="color: blue; margin: 0;">PROFESSIONAL SCHOOLS</h2> [] Main [x] Branch Digos _____
VALIDATION SHEET FOR RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE	

Name of Evaluator : **LEILANIE L. TINGZON, EdD.**
 Degree : Doctor of Education
 Position : _____
 Number of Years of Teaching : _____
 To the Evaluator : Please check the appropriate box for your ratings
 Points of Equivalent :

5 - Excellent	2 - Fair
4 - Very Good	1 - Poor
3 - Good	

ITEMS	5	4	3	2	1
1. Clarity of Directions and Items The vocabulary level, language, structure and conceptual level of questions suit the level of participants. The directions and the items are written in a clear and simple language.		/			
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6. Objectivity Each item questions only one specific answer or measures only one behavior and no aspect of the questionnaire is a suggestion of the researcher.	/				
7. Scale and Evaluation Rating Scale The scale adapted is appropriate for the items.	/				

Title of Approved Research: **"THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDGE AND INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES"**

Name of Researcher: **JUVIE O. BANGCASAN**

Research Adviser: **LEIZEL V. CHAN, Ed.D.**

Date of Evaluation of the Questionnaire: **July 31, 2021**

Remarks of the Evaluator: **Follow comments**

LEILANIE L. TINGZON, EdD.
 Signature Above Printed Name

<p>PROFESSIONAL SCHOOLS UM The University of Mindanao</p>	[] Main [] Branch _____ VALIDATION SHEET FOR RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE					
Name of Evaluator Dr. Mary Ann E. Tarusan Degree Ph.D. AL Position R.C-Offsite Number of Years of Teaching 35 years To the Evaluator Please check the appropriate box for your ratings						
Points of Equivalent	5- Excellent 4- Very Good 3- Good	2- Fair 1- Poor				
ITEMS		5	4	3	2	1
1.	Clarity of Directions and Items The vocabulary level, language, structure and conceptual level of questions suit the level of participants. The directions and the items are written in a clear and simple language.		/			
2.	Presentation and Organization of Items The items are presented and organized in logical manner.			/		
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6.	Objectivity Each item questions only one specific answer or measures only one behavior and no aspect of the questionnaire is a suggestion of the researcher.		/			
7.	Scale and Evaluation Rating Scale The scale adapted is appropriate for the items.			/		
Title of Approved Research : THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDGE AND INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES						
Name of Researcher: <u>Juvie Bangcasan</u>						
Research Adviser: <u>Dr. Lizeal Chan</u>						
Date of Evaluation of the Questionnaire: <u>9-20-21</u>						
Remarks of the Evaluator: I suggest to use the word 'manifested' instead of observed. Please put also the values 5 4 3 2 1 immediately above your boxes.						
Mary Ann E. Tarusan _____ Signature Above Printed Name						

UM
The University of Mindanao

PROFESSIONAL SCHOOLS
[] Main [] Branch

VALIDATION SHEET FOR RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE

Name of Evaluator : Elden D. Orbeta, PhD
 Degree : Doctor of Philosophy
 Position : Education Program Supervisor
 Number of Years of Teaching : 14
 To the Evaluator :
 Points of Equivalent :

Please check the appropriate box for your ratings
 5 - Excellent 2 - Fair
 4 - Very Good 1 - Poor
 3 - Good

ITEMS	1	2	3	4	5
1. Clarity of Directions and Items The vocabulary level, language, structure and conceptual level of questions suit the level of participants. The directions and the items are written in a clear and simple language.				-	
2. Presentation and Organization of Items The items are presented and organized in logical manner.					-
3. Suitability of Items The item is appropriate and represents the substance of the research. The questions are designed to determine the conditions, knowledge, perception and attitudes that are supposed to be measured.				-	
4. Adequateness of Items per Category or Indicator The items represent the coverage of research adequately. The questions per area category are adequate representations of all the questions needed for research.					-
5. Attainment of Purpose The instrument fulfills the objectives for which it was constructed.					-
6. Objectivity Each item questions only one specific answer or measures only one behavior and no aspect of the questionnaire is a suggestion of the researcher.					-
7. Scale and Evaluation Rating Scale The scale adapted is appropriate for the items.					-

Title of the Research Questionnaire : The mediating effect of Employee Motivation on the relationship between Professional Knowledge and Instructional Strategies

Name of Researcher : Juvia O. Burgosan

Date of Evaluation of the Questionnaire : Oct. 11, 2021

Remarks of the evaluator : Kindly see and follow some corrections. Pls. abide with the ethical standards in conducting the study. Good luck!

ELDEN D. ORBETA, PhD
 Signature Above Printed Name

APPENDIX E

UMERC CERTIFICATE OF APPROVAL

ETHICS REVIEW COMMITTEE (UMERC)

Ground Floor, Professional Schools Building
 Ma-a Matina Campus, Davao City
 Telephone: (082)305-0640 local 189
 umethicsreviewer@umindanao.edu.ph

FORM 2.6

Certificate of Approval

Date February 3, 2022

This is to certify that the following protocol and related documents have been granted approval by the University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee for implementation.

UMERC Protocol No.	UMERC-2022-007	Sponsor Protocol No	N/A
Principal Investigator/s	JUVIE O. BANGCASAN	Sponsor	N/A
Title	THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDGE AND INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES		
Protocol Version No.	2	Version Date	January 28, 2022
ICF Version No.	1	Version Date	January 9, 2022
Other documents			
Members of research team			
Study sites	Davao Region		
Type of review	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Expedited <input type="checkbox"/> Full board	Duration of Approval: January 29 - May 29, 2022	Approved Meeting Date: January 29, 2022
UMERC Chairperson	Signature	Date	
HELEN Q. OMBLERO, DSD		January 29, 2022	

Investigator Responsibilities after Approval:

- Submit document amendments for UMERC approval before implementing them
- Submit SAE and SUSAR reports to the UMERC
- Submit progress report every ____ months
- Submit final report after completion of protocol procedures at the study site
- Report protocol deviation/ violation
- Comply with all relevant international and national guidelines and regulations
- Abide by the principles of good clinical practice and ethical research

ETHICS REVIEW COMMITTEE (UMERC)

Ground Floor, Professional Schools Building
 Ma-a Matina Campus, Davao City
 Telephone: (082)305-0640 local 189
 umethicsreviewer@umindanao.edu.ph

Received by:
 Name JUVIE O. BANGCASAN
 Signature _____

Date February 3, 2022

APPENDIX F

PUBLIC FORUM CERTIFICATE

**CERTIFICATE
OF APPRECIATION**

is given to

JUVIE O. BANGCASAN

as RESOURCE SPEAKER

*during the Online Public Research Forum with the theme
“Inspiring Change and Innovation in Education: A Research Forum”*

*Given this 18th day of October 2022 at the
Professional Schools, University of Mindanao, Davao City*

JOEL B. TAN, DBA
Research Coordinator

SITTI ROGAIYA L. APADAN, RSW
*AVP, Community Extension
& Outreach*

EUGENIO S. GUHAO, JR., DM
Dean

APPENDIX G

EDITOR'S CERTIFICATION

*Professional Schools
Ground Floor, PS Building
Matina, Davao City
Telephone: (082) 297-6115*

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that the manuscript of **Ms. Juvie O. Bangcasan** entitled, "The Mediating Effect of Employee Motivation on the Relationship Between Professional Knowledge and Instructional Strategies" has been checked and edited by the undersigned in accordance with the standard mechanics, format, spacing, and references set by the university.

This certification is issued on July 8, 2023.

DAN O. GOMEZ, EdD
Reader

APPENDIX H
INFORMED CONCENT FORM (ICS)

University of Mindanao Informed Consent Form (ICF)
UMERC - 006 Rev. 01 / December 1, 2016
Approved by:
Control No.:
University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee
Matina, Davao City
Informed Consent Form for The Mediating Effect of Employee Motivation on the Relationship Between Professional Knowledge and Instructional Strategies
Name of the Researcher JUVIE O. BANGCASAN
Institution: University of Mindanao-Panabo City
INTRODUCTION
You are invited to participate in a research study conducted by Juvie O. Bangcasan, at the University of Mindanao, because you fit the inclusion criteria for informants of our study.
Your participation is completely voluntary. Please read the information below, and ask questions about anything you do not understand, before deciding whether to participate. Please take as much time as you need to read the consent form. You may also decide to discuss participation with your family or friends.
If you decide to participate, you will be asked to sign this form. You will be given a copy of this form.
PURPOSE OF THE STUDY
This study aims to predict the mediating effect of employee motivation on the relationship between professional knowledge and instructional strategies of TLE teachers in the division of Davao de Oro.
STUDY PROCEDURES
If you volunteer to participate in this study, you will be asked to participate by answering the survey questionnaire which you can finish in less than 30 minutes.
POTENTIAL RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS
You may feel discomfort during the course of the interview because of the sensitive nature of the topic being studied. You may opt not to answer questions which make you feel any psychological or emotional distress or you can withdraw as a participant of the study if you feel that you cannot discuss the information that is asked of you. The researchers value your participation and will place your welfare as their highest priority during the course of the study.
POTENTIAL BENEFITS TO PARTICIPANTS AND/OR TO SOCIETY
This study can generate relevant information which can be useful to public and private administrators, human resource managers, and policy-makers. The results, discussion, and findings from this study can spark evidence-based information which can be used by government agencies such as the Department of Education, school administrators, teachers, students, parents, and future researcher.
CONFIDENTIALITY
We will keep your records for this study confidential as far as permitted by law. Any identifiable information obtained in connection with this study will remain confidential, except if necessary to protect your rights or welfare. This certificate means that the researcher can resist the release of information about your participation to people who are not connected with the study. When the results of the research are published or discussed in conferences, no identifiable information will be used.
PARTICIPATION AND WITHDRAWAL
Your participation is voluntary. Your refusal to participate will involve no penalty or loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled. You may withdraw your consent at any time and discontinue participation without penalty. You are not waiving any legal claims, rights or remedies because of your participation in this research study.
INVESTIGATOR'S CONTACT INFORMATION
If you have any questions or concerns about the research, please feel free to contact the researcher at the University of Mindanao, Davao City through telephone number or mobile phone number 09296030284, or through email at jbangcasan@umindanao.edu.ph; or if you need to see her, she can be located at the Office of the Mapapat National High School, Davao de Oro.
RIGHTS OF RESEARCH PARTICIPANT
If you have questions, concerns, or complaints about your right as a research participant or the research in general and are unable to contact the research team, or if you want to talk to someone independent of the research team, please contact the University of Mindanao Professional Schools at 205-06-45.
RESEARCH PARTICIPANT'S CONSENT
I have read the information provided above. I have been given a chance to ask questions. My questions have been answered to my satisfaction, and I agree to participate in this study. I have been given a copy of this form. I can withdraw my consent at any time and discontinue participation without penalty.
Signature above Printed Name of Participant
Date Signed
To be accomplished by the Researcher Obtaining Consent:
I have explained the research to the participant and answered all of his/her questions. I believe that he/she understands the information described in this document and freely consents to participate.
Name of Person Obtaining Consent
Date Signed